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**CLINICAL WORK PREPAREDNESS AND JOB SATISFACTION AMONG
CRITICAL CARE NURSES IN A TERTIARY HOSPITAL IN SAUDI ARABIA**

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This Special Project titled: “**CLINICAL WORK PREPAREDNESS AND JOB SATISFACTION AMONG CRITICAL CARE NURSE IN A TERTIARY HOSPITAL IN SAUDI ARABIA**” is hereby accepted by the Faculty of Management and Development Studies, U.P. Open University, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree Course.

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Biographical Sketch

Ms. Darroca has worked in Saudi Arabia for 23years. She has been an advanced trainer and mentor at the Neonatal Intensive Care Unit (NICU). She developed critical policies and procedural strategies as trainer and formulated orientation guidelines, in her pursuit for quality learning. She has been a Head Nurse for more than a decade and a Unit Quality Head Coordinator. She constantly assessed and monitor clinical issues that affect the delivery of client care, where she is most passionate and continuously demonstrate her dedication towards excellence.

Ms. May Aileen Bacting-Darroca graduated with a Master of Arts in Nursing from the University of the Philippines, Open University, and a Bachelor of Science in Nursing from the University of Iloilo. She is presently employed as the head nurse at a prominent Saudi Arabian tertiary hospital's neonatal intensive care unit.

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DEDICATION

I dedicate this work to my family and friends. A very special feeling of gratitude to my late mother, Angeles Juanito Bacting, for all the love, support, and encouragement to pursue my dreams. Although she is no longer in this world, her memories continue to regulate my life and my source of inspiration.

I am also dedicating this humble accomplishment to my only son, Arvin Peter Darroca, the source of my strength, love, and for being there for me throughout this process.

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The Researcher

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ABSTRACT

A number of factors are associated with work preparedness and the degree of satisfaction among nurses working in hospitals. This study set out to investigate the degree of contentment among nurses employed at a tertiary hospital's intensive care unit. A total of 149 nurses who worked in intensive care units made up the study's sample. The Casey-Fink Graduate Nurse Experience Survey was used to gather data.

Out of the 149 nurses, 72 (48.3%) were working in the Neonatal and Pediatric; while 36 (24.2%) in the Medical-Surgical ICU with 77 (51.7%) and with 5-10 years length of hospital experience. The findings indicated that the areas with the lowest levels of satisfaction were leadership, decision-making, employee well-being, promotion, and pay level, while the areas with the greatest levels were colleague satisfaction and job satisfaction. It also demonstrates that there is a strong correlation between the nurses' job happiness and every facet of clinical readiness.

Keywords: Clinical Work Preparedness, Job Satisfaction, Critical Care

Chapter I

THE RESEARCH PROBLEM

Background of the Study

Critical care nurses play a vital role in the patient's care (Carayon & Gurses, 2005). Many key nursing skills must be mastered by all nurses who are new to acute critical care units. Establishing a setting that supports the acquisition of the necessary skills, which is essential to guaranteeing clinical competence. Nonetheless, there were few studies that concentrated on clinical education for certified nurse's beginning their first shift in acute critical care (Chan, 2012).

Nurses who would like to work in the intensive care unit for the first time must be equipped with the mastery of critical skills. Competence in clinical work is an important component in providing an environment which is conducive to learning. However, studies for qualified nurses joining the critical care unit were found as posited in the study of (Chan, 2012).

While working in an intensive care unit, nurses must continue to focus on their professional growth due to ongoing technological advancements and modifications to nursing and medical practice. Huggins (2013) found that in order to become a successful practitioner, intensive care nurses must continuously acquire new information and abilities through a lifetime learning process that involves opportunity, learning, and result. Furthermore, Huggins (2013) noted that the critical care nurses' ultimate goal in their education was to become competent practitioners who could provide patients with high-quality care.

The changing face of the medical and nursing profession along with the continuous

technology advances, has prompted the need for incessant professional growth of the assigned staff within the environment of intensive critical care. The findings of Huggins (2013) revealed that for one to become a competent nurse, there is a need to continually provide an opportunity to upgrade the skills and knowledge through lifelong learning. Moreover, Huggins pointed out, that to provide quality patient care to a higher level, nurses must practice frequently the skills set by the health care industry.

Lambert and Glacken (2015) expounded that nursing profession is often associated with the learning by doing practice, as it involves appreciation and acknowledgement and appreciation of one experience in learning, which may at times be taken for granted. Recognizing that learning in critical care is unconstrained and unanticipated, devising a scheme to ensure that opportunities for learning are maximized and the risk of disorganized information is minimized.

A common scenario of patients at risk are just few of the unfavorable events in critical care. The nurses' knowledge and judgement to every critical situation is of prime importance in the prevention and mitigation of adverse events. Another related challenge for critical care is to improve nursing competencies in almost all countries of the world, not sparing the tertiary hospital of Tabuk, KSA.

The researcher has been working in one of the Intensive Critical Care Units of King Fahad Specialist Hospital (KFSH) which conforms to the Guidelines of the Ministry of Health-Saudi Arabia and the CBAHI (Central Board for Accreditation of Healthcare Institution) in Tabuk, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. As a neophyte critical care nurse, the researcher experienced a feeling of fear and some degree of difficulty in the performance of tasks. The feeling of ambivalence is evident whether the performance of job lead to patient satisfaction or otherwise. Compared to other hospital unit assignments, life in the critical care unit is incredibly challenging as most patients are with life- threatening

conditions that necessitate urgent attention and treatment. This would include patients on life-saving machine with ventilators, oxygen therapy, dialysis, nutritional support, central venous /arterial catheter or with cardiac monitor that need constant care. Moreover, patients in critical care unit are with diverse medications and multiple life- saving infusions. Critical care staffs are required to be multitaskers, knowledgeable who pay utmost attention to detail and are specialized in patient care of critically ill patients.

A nurse assigned in the critical care unit undergoes on-the-job orientation which would normally last for three (3) months. During this three- month period, they need to complete a competency at the same time may perform tasks under the supervision of the senior nurse. In the operations of the unit, both new and old nurses are expected to follow the procedure guidelines, duties, and responsibilities as well as the policies of other departments. All medical and other hospital employees are obliged to follow the rules and regulations of the hospital. The expectations for the senior nurses may not be the same from that of the newly assigned ones as the latter performed tasks as they learn and relearn the expected competencies.

As a nurse manager, the researcher has been confronted with similar work issues as the new ones, that is, performing less than what the index of competencies required. It seems that such performance had been brought about by incompetency and inexperienced practitioner– a by-product of insufficient knowledge and non-mastery of nursing skills for patients with literally intensive health care needs. The scenario has even worsened with the nurses' anxiety of committing mistakes, uncertainty in workload and roles transition which resulted in stress and substandard performance in health care, eventually leading to very low work motivation and performance outcome.

From this perspective, the researcher is motivated to carry out a study which seeks to determine the factors associated with the clinical work preparedness (skills and

procedure performance, comfort and confidence, their work environment, the challenge of changing roles), as well as their job satisfaction (concerning pay, vacation time, workload, schedule, benefits, monthly weekends off, the ability to choose shift work, the quantity of support and feedback received, and prospects for professional growth).

Comprehending these factors in clinical preparedness and job satisfaction may lower the rate of staff turn-over in the critical care units. With the outcome of the study, this may be of use as the basis for the innovation, decrease attrition and increase productivity as well as patient satisfaction. Thus, the study on the factors associated with clinical work preparedness and job satisfaction becomes more relevant.

Statement of the Problem

The purpose of this study was to identify the variables that are related to critical care nurses' levels of job satisfaction and clinical work readiness in a tertiary hospital in Tabuk, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia.

Specifically, the study seeks answers to the following questions:

1. What is the level of clinical work preparedness of the critical care nurses in terms of –

1.1 Skills and procedure performance;

1.2 Comfort and confidence; and

1.3 Work environment and difficulty of role transition?

2. What is the level of job satisfaction of the critical care nurses in terms of

2.1 Salary;

2.2 Vacation;

2.3 Work load;

2.4 Work schedule;

2.5 Benefits package;

2.6 Weekends off per month;

2.7 Opportunity to choose shifts work;

2.8 Amount of encouragement and feedback; and

2.9 Opportunities for career advancement?

3. Is there a significant relationship between the level of clinical work preparedness and the socio-demographic characteristics of the critical care nurses in terms of –

3.1 Age;

3.2 Civil Status;

3.3 Educational attainment;

3.4 Length of experience in the intensive critical care;

3.5 Length of hospital experience; and

3.6 Type of intensive critical care unit?

4. Is there a significant relationship between the job satisfaction and the socio-demographic characteristics of the critical care nurses in terms of –

4.1 Age;

4.2 Civil Status;

4.3 Educational attainment;

4.4 Length of experience in the critical care;

4.5 Length of hospital experience; and

4.6 Type of critical care unit?

5. Is there a significant relationship between the level of clinical work preparedness and the job satisfaction of the critical care nurses?

Significance of the Study

Specifically, the study will benefit the following groups:

Human resource planners and managers of the Ministry of Health. The outcome of

the study will be used as basis in the planning process and in creating programs for the professional growth and development of the nurses assigned in critical area and other department in the hospital.

The nurse practitioner especially the Nursing Administration Personnel and other professional groups, in which the result of the study, will encourage them to formulate programs that will enhance staff preparedness, knowledge regarding policies and procedure guidelines in accordance with the laws and regulations on nursing profession. In the selection of nurses to be assigned to work in critical area and to consider nurse-patient ratio, workload, staffing- requirements. The nurse educator may create programs that promote a learning environment as well satisfaction in the job of nurses in critical care.

The researchers may develop a deeper understanding on how to take care of their patient for the enhancement of a better decision-making capabilities.

Further, the study will serve as a basis to benchmark in the review and update of the intensive critical care units' personnel programs and services particularly in the enhancement of meaningful and relevant clinical care learning programs.

Thus, to help address these existing gaps in literature and help improve the work preparedness among critical care nurses, the skills and procedure performance, comfort and confidence, work environment, and job satisfaction level of critical care nurses with regard to pay, vacation, workload, work schedule, number of weekends off per month, ability to select shift work, level of encouragement, and opportunities for career advancement will all be examined in this study.

Scope and Limitations of the Study

The study's objectives were restricted to identifying the variables linked to the degree of clinical work readiness and job contentment among 149 critical care nurses from Tabuk, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. The Casey-Fink Graduate Nurse Experience Survey (2006) from the University of Colorado Hospital was used as the model for the one-shot survey.

Data were subjected to descriptive and inferential analysis. Frequency counts, percentage, means, and standard deviation were used to describe the data. Chi-square test of association and Spearman rho. Levels of significance set at 5 percent were used to determine the differences in the relationships between clinical work preparedness and job satisfaction with the socio demographic characteristics of the intensive critical care nurses. Data were processed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS).

Operational Definition of Terms

To facilitate understanding of terms used in the study, these are defined operationally.

Age. This term refers to the age of the last birthday of the intensive critical care nurses in the tertiary government hospital in Tabuk, KSA. In this study, the age of nurses will be categorized as young (30 years old and younger), middle age (31 years old to 40 years old), and old (older than 40 years old).

Civil Status. This term refers to the marital status of the intensive critical care nurses in the tertiary government hospital and categorized as single, married, widow, and common-in-law.

Educational Attainment. This term refers to the formal schooling achieved by the new ICU nurses in the tertiary government hospital. In the study, the educational attainment of the nurses will be grouped as Diploma in Nursing, Bachelor of Science in

Nursing, and master's in nursing.

Length of Intensive Critical Care Experience. This term refers to the number of years or months the respondent has rendered intensive critical care nursing.

Length of Hospital Work Experience. This term refers to the number of years or months rendered by the respondent in the clinical practice particularly in the hospital. In the study, the length of hospital experience, is categorized with less than 5 years, 5 to 10 years, and more than 10 years.

Type of Intensive Critical Care Unit. The term refers to the unit where the intensive critical care nurses are assigned. The intensive care units in this study are divided into four categories: medical, which includes coronary care; surgical, which includes trauma and cardiovascular care; neonatal and pediatric; and medical-surgical.

Level of Clinical Work Preparedness. This term refers to the nurse's readiness to perform nursing care in hospital. In this study, verbal interpretation of preparedness simultaneously the same with extremely difficult or slightly prepared, moderately difficult, or moderately prepared and slightly difficult or extremely prepared in terms of skills and procedure performance, comfort and confidence in doing his task, work environment and difficulty with role transition among critical care nurses (Casey et al., 2006).

Level of Job Satisfaction. This term refers to the nurse's view of her contentment with her job, whether she likes the job or individual aspects of jobs. In this study, the term refers to the intensive critical care nurse's job contentedness in terms of salary, vacation, workload, work schedule, benefits package, weekends off per month, opportunity to choose shifts work, amount of encouragement and feedback, and opportunities for career advancement (Wilkin & Slevin, 2013).

Extremely unhappy, somewhat unsatisfied, neither satisfied nor dissatisfied, moderately content, and extremely satisfied were the assessments of the nurses' work satisfaction in this study.

Chapter II

THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

This chapter discusses the overview of the review of related literature, theoretical background, the conceptual framework, and the hypotheses of the study.

Review of Related Literature

This investigation on the clinical work preparedness and job satisfaction among intensive critical care nurses is based on the Theory of Reasoned Action (ToRA or TRA) developed by Martin Fishbein and Icek Ajzen in 1967. The purpose of the theory is to elucidate the relationship within the human action their behaviors and attitudes. Its main purpose is to predict an individual's conduct by taking into account their past opinions and behavioral intentions. An individual's decision-making process is contingent upon the consequences of their actions and the behavior they produce. The theory's main goal is to comprehend behavior by examining the fundamental stimulus that prompts an action. ToRA posited that at the main anticipation to perform a behavior is to know the person's intention. In addition, the acceptable behavior within an environment has an effect whether the person will perform the behavior. Moreover, the intention behind a certain activity precedes the actual behavior. This kind of intention, referred to as behavioral intention, stems from the conviction that engaging in the activity will produce a certain result. Because attitudes toward behaviors and subjective standards have an impact on these goals, behavioral intention is crucial to the theory.

The idea of reasoned action states that stronger aims lead to more effort to carry out the activity, which also increases the likelihood that the conduct will be carried out (Ajzen & Albarracín, 2007).

In the same study, several components in the preparedness of the nurse to be in the intensive critical care unit may lead to job satisfaction, just as job satisfaction may

enhance the level of preparedness of the nurses in their performance in the intensive care units.

Clinical Work Preparedness

Nurses are employed in the Critical Care Unit (CCU) according to the Composite Care and Management Venture, which demands technical and scientific competency from those whose decision-making and adoption of safe conducts are directly related to people's life or death. Determining these experts' abilities in high-complexity nursing care, such as that provided at the ICU, is crucial in this regard (Valentin et al., 2016).

Ensuring that patients with critical illnesses receive safe, high-quality treatment in the intricate setting of the critical care unit (CCU) is an ongoing problem. Patients are far more likely to suffer injury when complex medical procedures, numerous caregivers, and uncertainties are combined. A lot of CCU episodes that include patient injury (adverse events) or patient risk of harm (near-misses) may be prevented and have several facets. Examinations of CCU data obtained from self-reports of interdisciplinary occurrences show that human-related elements, such as the clinician's expertise and knowledge, frequently play a role in adverse outcomes (Schmalenberg & Kramer, 2017).

To effectively establish ways to lower the risk of injury to patients, it is imperative that nurses comprehend their involvement in preventing negative situations. One way to verify physicians' ability in a particular field is through specialized certification programs.

The relationship between specialized certification and competency in the medical field has not yet been investigated. A new field of inquiry in nursing is the connection between certification and competence (Pronovost et al., 2016).

In critical care units, adverse events that put patients at risk of damage frequently

occur. The amount of expertise and discernment possessed by clinicians seems to have an impact on the prevention, mitigation, and development of adverse events. Studies suggest a potential correlation between clinical skill and a nurse's specialized certification. A relatively recent topic of research in nursing examines the connection between specialist certification, clinical competency of registered nurses, and patient safety (Pronovost, 2012).

Joshi et al. (2016) assessed nurses' knowledge and competence levels in order to produce evidence on the quality of newborn nursing. 36 of the 600 recently hired nurses participated in cross-sectional observational research on newborn nursing at random. The study's findings also showed that 36 nurses in all, many of whom held a BSc in nursing, participated in the research.

At the pre-service level, among the individuals, one-third had no clinical posting in the NICU. Over 60% of nurses scored highly in knowledge, whereas a comparable percentage had subpar general abilities. More than half of the nursing staff perform bag and mask ventilation, intravenous medicine administration, and orogastric feeding with mediocre hand cleanliness, temperature recording, and hypothermia prevention abilities, but poorly with weight recording. The knowledge, skill and preparedness scores were found with no correlation. The nurses' median self-preparedness scores indicated that they may have overestimated their ability to conduct the newborn procedures. The team came to the conclusion that the nurses needed attention since they were not adequately skilled to conduct the different newborn procedures that come with working in a critical care unit.

Critical Care Units (CCUs) are hiring new nurse graduates without the provision of training in order to become more competent. The workplace preparedness of recent graduates joining the intensive care unit (ICU) was examined in a study by Lewis-Pierre

et al. (2014) from the viewpoints of managers, clinical educators, preceptors, and recent graduates. The qualitative approach used in this study was the Grounded theory with a total of 24 in-depth interviews. There are four emerging themes from the Novice Nurse Embracing the ICU theory (NNEIT): (a) accepting the new position in the ICU; (b) experiencing performance uncertainty or anxiety to the extreme; (c) adjusting to the ICU; and (d) assuming the role of the new ICU RN. The hypothesis came to the conclusion that the research would help resolve the debate over the knowledge and abilities needed by new nurses joining the intensive care unit.

Graduates must change their perspectives from those of students to those of critical care nurses. 40% of recent grads committed prescription mistakes, according to a National Council of the State Board of Nursing (NCSBN) report (Moscaritolo, 2015). The complicated, multifarious patients and duties that the recent grads are handling are directly linked to these mistakes (2013). Whether recent nursing graduates are ready to work in the complex critical care unit is a common worry. As to the 2015 Future of Nursing report, orientation programs can facilitate the assimilation of novice nurses into the field and lower the attrition rate. Transitional barriers to new graduate orientation are added by technological innovation, prioritizing, training capacity, and socialization to the intensive care unit (Graham, Hall, & Sigurdson, 2016). Experienced nurses are concerned about the new graduates' lack of critical care training. The ICU's new RN grads' preparedness for the workplace differs depending on the demands of the company and financial obligations.

Trepanier et al. (2012) state that the expense of a critical care residency program for a new graduate orientation might amount to up to \$36,960 per intern for an organization. After orientation at the intensive care unit, recently graduated registered nurses are overwhelmed and do not know what clinical standards and competencies are

required to manage the complex critical care patient population (Proulx & Bourcier, 2018).

According to Gaylak (2017), nursing programs at universities place a strong emphasis on theory, but there don't appear to be enough practical resources available to give recent graduates enough critical care exposure to transition into a clinical ICU situation. In order to attract and retain new nurses, it is essential to understand the particular competency criteria for graduate nurse practice in the intensive care unit. Clinical competence is necessary to improve nurse decision-making and patient care outcomes (Tilley, 2012).

ICU nurses must possess in-depth knowledge to effectively treat patients who are unstable and react to abrupt changes in the patient's state (Storesunda & McMurray, 2014). In this type of practice, nurses evaluate patient data, facilitate treatments guided by decision-making, and develop individualized care plans for each patient. In order to support the progression of a newly graduated registered nurse into a competent ICU nurse, seasoned nurses must provide support, direction, and skill development. Given the scarcity of RNs and the flood of recent graduates into the field, meeting their educational demands is of utmost importance. There's a clear lack of critical care practice preparation among recent nursing graduates.

The ICU of the hospital is a high skill unit, so nurses are anticipated to show the utmost care and demonstrate competent practice to patients (Chesnutt & Everhart, 2017). In 2016, Camire, Moyen, and Stelfox came to the conclusion that 10.5 out of 100 patients in the critical care unit had medication mistakes. The uneven training of recent graduates assigned to the ICU is the cause of this drug mistake. Studies on the preparedness of the ICU workforce were scarce, despite earlier researchers focusing on the broad idea of recent graduates joining the industry.

Nursing competencies to work at ICU

Nursing care management

According to selected studies, nurses' function at the ICU is to plan and organize various tasks through division, the work that needs to be accomplished, during their shift and at times the shift of their colleague (Adhikari, et al., 2015). Consequently, planning for the care and management of patients, as well as carrying out some administrative duties, fall under the purview of ICU nurses.

High-complexity nursing care delivery

Distributed among the health team members is the patient care activity at the ICU. According to two studies, the nature of nursing job necessitates paying attention to a variety of care demands, including complexity, delivery, and the work environment.

As expected, Nurses are responsible for providing treatment that is more practically difficult, requiring both scientific understanding and quick decision-making ability. When providing nursing care to patients who are extremely complicated, nurses have the opportunity to become involved, learn about self-accomplishment, develop dedication, strengthen their relationship with the patient, and contribute to the provision of high-quality care. Nursing employment include providing patients with complex care directly and coordinating the several tasks of the healthcare team (Beckmann et al., 2016).

Decision making

The management and care coordination duties of nurses must be founded on their ability to make decisions while utilizing resources including personnel, supplies, procedures, and practices.

Understanding the organization and its mission, assessing the actual needs of

users, and work-based performance on planning that covers specific information and ideas and ways to put them into practice, as well as feasible resources, defining the parties involved and the steps to be followed, scheduling and involving different hierarchical levels, are some of the steps required to achieve the decision-making competencies (Benner, 2014).

Making decisions requires critical thinking about scenarios based on study and evaluation of the perspectives of each action plan and its development. This technique is based mostly on logical and intuitive reasoning and judgment. One of the administrative knowledge areas to be learned is the decision-making process, which includes goal-setting, alternative search, selection, implementation, and evaluation. Another is the culture and power structures of organizations.

Three particular studies highlight the decision-making skills of nurses. According to one study, the process is a part of the everyday lives of nurses and is impacted by a variety of factors, including institutional culture and behavior patterns. It is also noted that nurses prioritize professional expertise and scientific knowledge when making judgments, basing them on adhering to the institution's norms and maintaining the unit's organization and functionality (Benner, 2014; Buffum & Brandon, 2017; Casey, 2006).

The other research on this subject suggests that decision-making is an integrative tactic that aims to include and collaborate. As such, nurses should use creativity when making decisions in order to adapt human and material resources and provide high-quality care (Couchman et al., 2017; Chan, 2012). This viewpoint will make more and more cooperation and employee involvement inside the company necessary.

Nursing leadership

According to a study in 2017 by Daughtery and colleagues, leadership is one of the

key competencies that health workers nowadays need to cultivate.

Leadership competence is often developed through the complexity of the imposed tasks on nurses at the ICU and managing care practices. Since nurses work night shifts most of the time, they have the opportunity to gain leadership experience in a setting where real-world scenarios demand competence, preparation, and insight from their nurses. Effective dedication, empathy, communication, accountability, decision-making ability, and management are all necessary components of leadership.

According to one research, the interactive intensive care unit (ICU) setting, where choices must be made quickly and assertively, frequently results in an authoritarian posture rather than a participative one. Every nurse in the team has a remarkable quality. In this situation, nurses should ensure that care adheres to set goals and modify their leadership approach in response to variations (Henderson-Everhardus, 2014).

In one of the studies, situational leadership was based on the single appropriate leadership style for any situation. These four leadership philosophies are assign, share, convince, and decide. The study's findings showed a tendency toward greater participatory leadership, which includes the ability to influence and communicate care choices to other experts; in other words, nurses may share their decisions, thoughts, and the decision-making process with other professionals. However, the defined paradigm still remains, wherein nurses provide precise instructions and actively monitor the work of the specialists they supervise (Lewis-Pierre et al., 2014).

In order to build responsible leadership where trust and an unwavering quest for knowledge are valued, ICU nurses should appreciate each member of the team. However, the significance of these experts' ongoing education increases when it comes to meeting the demands of the team and the organization.

Communication

Communication is one of the resources the ICU needs for health collaboration. In order to achieve the goals of the communicators, stray from basic communication knowledge, pay attention to both verbal and nonverbal cues during interactions, act impartially and clearly, and develop self-awareness in the quest for a more genuine life, one can conceptualize competent communication as an interpersonal process. When looking at nurses' management work process from the perspective of an intensive care unit, effective communication is essential to sufficient and fruitful interactions.

Effective communication is crucial for managers. Effective communication is essential for the efficient operation of work units and the organization as a whole. It helps to organize, recognize, and solve problems.

To effectively address the requirements of patients and family members, communication techniques must be developed. In order to provide organized and structured nursing care, researchers emphasized the significance of fusing theoretical knowledge with sensitivity in order to inform family members about what occurs in the ICU and encourage them to express their emotions. As a result of these studies, when relatives of ICU patients in hospitals discussed communication with the health team, it became evident that professionals needed to clarify their messages and offer more details. The nursing team was mentioned as a potential resource for this assistance.

One strategy to alter and enhance care is communication. In this way, evaluation, planning, and communication are activities that are included in day-to-day ICU work and are essential to each choice or action (Dennison, 2015).

Continuing/permanent education

In the intensive care unit, staff members are required to be able to recognize and

address physiological changes in patients, reduce anxiety in both patients and family members, make use of the technology available in the setting, and promote interdisciplinary collaboration. Along with other members of the nursing team, nurses are in charge of organizing and maintaining the surroundings (Hunt & Ellison, 2017). Nonetheless, it takes work and commitment on the part of these experts to oversee the competency growth of their peers. Activities related to continuous and permanent education are seen to be one means of ensuring that the nursing team's care competency is maintained.

The research conducted by Hurley & Snowden (2018) verified which internal CEU programs are developed for the nursing staff, when they are started, and by whom. It was also looked at what formal external continuing education activities nurses have participated in.

Out of all the ICUs under examination, 34 (79.1%) responded that they gave the nursing team particular first training, which most often took up to one month (44.2%), according to the data. Out of the ICUs, 18 (41.9%) provide recycling programs that mostly concentrate on updating patients on diseases and reviewing skills and routines. Programs for recycling and initial training are mostly created by ICU nurses. Thus, one may contend that continuous education was necessary to attain professional competency development, which comprises improvement and recycling activities.

In the context of nurses' job and professional development, it is essential to stress that professional education is viewed as a form of permanent education (PE). Since PE includes management, care delivery, education, and critical reflection on routine work practices to bring about changes in the mindset and behavior of the health team, it was also highlighted as a participatory management method for ICU work and care.

Together with the role of universities and institutional policies, the National Curricular Guidelines (NCGs) mention the practice of permanent education competency as a duty of health professionals. Through ongoing skill and competency development in line with the epidemiological environment and the demands of health situations, nurses participate in the permanent education process with the goal of developing attitudes that result in qualitative changes in their work process (Hunt & Ellison, 2017).

Human resource management

In the course of their profession, nurses must be able to take the initiative and manage personnel as well as material and physical resources.

In one study, nursing staff dimensioning is noteworthy with regard to nursing human resource management in ICU. It is seen as a means of meeting patient needs for care, which helps to preserve positive working circumstances and, as a result, the health of nursing staff members who deal with traumatic situations—suffering and death—on a regular basis (Hunt & Ellison, 2017).

ICU nurses must link the complexity level required by clients with the capacity and preparedness of their collaborators for nursing human resource management. Team workers will be able to develop and enhance their nursing care delivery knowledge, abilities, and attitudes as a result.

Material resource management

In order to ensure that user care is not disrupted by insufficient material resources, material resource management is defined as the flow of programming (material classification, standardization, specification, and preview), purchasing (quality control and public tender processes), reception, storage, distribution, and control activities (Kelly & Ahern, 2017).

The management of health facilities and services, including the administration of human and material resources and the planning and provision of resources required to meet patients' requirements, is one of the functions that nurses carry out as part of their management process.

Nurses are important in managing material resources, especially in higher tech services like ICUs where there are more complicated patients being cared for and high tech and care must work together. This information is consistent with a study that found that nurses manage material resources to oversee the whole flow of supplies needed for nursing care on a daily basis in the ICU.

The best nursing experts to handle this service are nurses, who can open and choose the best resources for providing patients and the complete healthcare team with competent and safe treatment. In addition to performing quality and waste control tasks, nurses also evaluate materials, monitor expensive items, and provide orientation on proper material usage.

Given the foregoing, these professionals require an understanding of material use control in order to act as a liaison between the nursing and health teams, facilitating the communication required for material forecasts and purchasing. This will allow them to determine the best material to deliver high-quality care to the clients for whom they are accountable for job satisfaction.

Previous studies have indicated that a primary concern for both nurses and healthcare administrators is work satisfaction. Healthcare facilities frequently struggle with nursing turnover, which is linked to increased expenses for the company as well as decreased patient and nurse satisfaction and safety (Jones & Gate, 2017). The issue of nursing turnover is still there and will likely get worse in the upcoming years as the

healthcare sector expands.

The total nursing turnover rate for bedside nurses is 14.2%, according to the 2014 National Healthcare & RN Retention Report (Nursing Solutions, Inc. [NSI], 2014). The reasons that have been shown to have the most effects on this turnover include a sense of being overworked, a lack of opportunity for growth, a decline in recognition or respect, a lack of clarity in one's function, a lack of trust or collaboration with coworkers, and poor management communication (Hunt, 2016).

In North America and other developed nations, the nurse shortage is at crisis proportions and is only getting worse (Sawatzky & Enns, 2015). One million nurses are expected to be in short supply by 2025 (Hunt, 2016). Specialty sectors, including the Critical Care Units, are more affected by this problem than other nursing areas.

Because of its unpredictable character, lack of established patient care loads, growing nurse-patient ratios, and variety of illnesses and injuries, the Critical Care Unit presents a unique work environment (Sawatzky & Enns, 2015). The amount of care provided is greatly impacted by nurse turnover. Longer patient stays and worse rates of risk-adjusted mortality were seen in healthcare institutions with high turnover rates (22%–44%) (Jones & Gates, 2017).

The entire unit's structure is impacted by a high rate of nurse turnover, which may be a sign of decreased job satisfaction and lead to more employee alienation and turnover. The cohesiveness of the unit's staff has an impact on patient satisfaction, which is frequently used as a gauge of the quality of care. Patient satisfaction declines when there is a high rate of nurse turnover due to a lack of cohesiveness (Bae, Mark, & Fried, 2015). Nurse turnover is also linked to financial expenditures. The company may lose twice the nurse's yearly income if only one nurse leaves (Hunt, 2016). Retraining a

specialist nurse, such a Critical Care nurse, can cost an organization up to \$100,000, while keeping one nurse on staff can save the company \$200,000. These findings are reported by Hairr, Salisbury, Johannsson, and Redfern-Vance (2014). Investigating strategies to keep nurses by raising job satisfaction is important because of the financial savings a hospital may achieve by keeping one nurse on staff. Nurse attrition not only hurts the organization's bottom line but also has a severe effect on the current nursing workforce. The increasing patient workload for current personnel will cause stress, which will in turn cause poorer job satisfaction (Ramoo, Abdullah & Piaw, 2013). The negative effects of turnover on the organization—such as greater workloads for current personnel, less patient satisfaction, and lower quality of care—are made worse by lower levels of satisfaction. According to Sawatzky and Enns (2015), there are economic costs associated with worker turnover, lower staff morale, and the first decline in productivity of new hires. Reduced service quality, higher staffing costs, patient attrition, more auxiliary staff turnover, and higher absenteeism and accident rates are some additional negative consequences of nurse turnover (Hunt, 2016). All of these detrimental consequences of employee turnover on the healthcare facility and its staff point to the necessity of examining existing satisfaction levels in order to create efficient plans to reduce turnover in the critical care units.

The most reliable indicator of nurses' intention to stay has been shown to be job satisfaction, which is a complicated issue influenced by a variety of circumstances (Liu, Zhang, Ye, Zhu, Cao, Lu & Li, 2015). Liu et al. (2015) defined work satisfaction as an individual's total sentiments about their job, whereas Wang et al. (2012) defined it as the extent to which an employee feels positively about their employment. Though few studies specifically focus on nurses in the Critical Care Unit, several indicate favorable associations between satisfaction and intend to stay (Liu et al., 2015). Critical Care Unit

(CCU)-specific job satisfaction data is essential for nurse supervisors creating retention plans for CCU staff. According to Ramoo et al. (2013), job satisfaction is a multifaceted notion that might be difficult to define since it varies from person to person. Because it depends on both the nature of the work itself and the individual's expectations of what the job should give, job satisfaction is a subjective variable (Ramoo et al., 2013).

Given that work happiness is contingent upon an individual's expectations, demographic considerations must be taken into account while assessing job satisfaction. According to Ramoo et al. (2013), job satisfaction is often correlated with age, gender, work experience, and educational attainment. As a result, this study will also examine demographic characteristics that are linked to work satisfaction.

As mentioned, the hospital system, local communities, and patient outcomes may all suffer as a result of the scarcity of critical care unit nurses. These factors make it crucial to have on board qualified CCU nurses. To address the nursing deficit in the CCU, nurse leaders need to concentrate their efforts on keeping their present staff members. Retention programs are built on an understanding of the elements that influence work satisfaction and encourage nurses to remain in their present roles. The idea that a nurse's intention to remain in or leave their present post is mostly determined by how satisfied they are with their work, and research indicates that a nurse's intention to leave is correlated with actual turnover. Nursing leadership will find great value in identifying factors that contribute to CCU nurses' work satisfaction when creating retention initiatives.

Factors Associated with Job Satisfaction

Ramoo et al. in 2013 carried out a study on intent to leave and work satisfaction at a teaching hospital in Malaysia. 141 nurses completed a self-administered questionnaire, and the findings showed that, overall, nurses had a moderate degree of job satisfaction and that, in turn, greater levels of job satisfaction are correlated with professional growth

and motivational factors. This supported their theory that workers who have more "challenging, interesting, and enriching" employment have greater job satisfaction ratings (Ramoo et al., 2013). According to Ramoo et al. (2013), the least satisfied factors were workload, staffing, decision-making, pay/benefits, and work scheduling. They also discovered, in line with other research in the field, that demographic variables like age, nursing education, and work experience affected job satisfaction. Another important conclusion of their study was that among nurses, job satisfaction significantly predicted their intention to leave (Ramoo et al., 2013).

Yen-Ju Lin, Wan, Hsu, Hung, Juan, and Lin (2012) conducted employee satisfaction surveys on 442 physicians and nurses from 119 hospital-based CCUs in Taiwan. The CCU culture was compared by the study's authors in relation to work satisfaction and intention to leave. The study's conclusions were that while work satisfaction was positively correlated with adhocracy culture, job satisfaction among CCU nurses was not influenced by culture. A dynamic, imaginative, and creative work environment that emphasizes leaders as creative and visionary, as well as quick expansion and resource acquisition, are the hallmarks of an adhocracy. According to research by Yen-Ju Lin et al. (2012), the majority of CCUs have a strong market culture and hierarchy, which nurses link to low work satisfaction. To improve work happiness, they urged CCU leadership to adopt an adhocracy culture.

Hairr, et al. (2014) carried out a study to investigate the connection between nurse retention, job satisfaction, and staffing. Seventy people responded to an online poll they used to gather data. Out of the seventy-one participants, nine were employed at a CCU. The workload and job satisfaction of nurses were found to have a poor association by the authors. Additionally, they discovered a negative correlation between retention and work satisfaction. This suggests that the likelihood of a nurse intending to quit their post increases with work satisfaction. Furthermore, 152 nurses from a Greek university

hospital participated in a study done in 2013 by Gaki, Kontodimopoulos, and Niakas. Their study set out to investigate the ways in which work-related characteristics and demographics affect nurses' motivation. The authors also looked into the connection between motivators and work happiness. According to Gaki et al. (2013), the primary predictor of nurses' motivation was their "achievements." Older nurses, those with more work experience, and those in higher hierarchical positions all reported greater levels of job satisfaction. Low satisfaction among nurses was caused by low pay and few opportunities for professional progression (Gaki et al., 2013).

Research on job satisfaction and intention to leave was carried out by El-Jardali, Dimassi, Dumit, Jamal, and Mouro (2015) among 1,739 nurses working in 69 hospitals in Lebanon. The purpose of the study was to precisely investigate how work satisfaction affects intention to leave. The McCloskey-Mueller Satisfaction Scale (MMSS), a question about intent to depart, and a demographic questionnaire were used to gather their data. According to their findings, 67.5% of the nurses polled intended to quit their jobs within the next one to three years, and 29.4% intended to leave nursing entirely. They discovered that nurses were the least happy with extrinsic benefits, and that the same things also affected their intention to quit the profession and their current job (El-Jardali et al., 2015).

It has been discovered that there are both positive and negative relationships between demographic traits and work satisfaction. Li and Lambert (2018) conducted descriptive research to identify the combination of demographic parameters that best predicted work satisfaction among critical care nurses from the People's Republic of China. Four self-report surveys were given to 102 critical care nurses from convenience samples drawn from four teaching hospitals spread across two central Chinese cities to achieve these goals. The factors that best predicted job satisfaction were years of nursing experience, busyness, and lack of assurance regarding patients' care. The results shed

light on the elements that must be taken into account and resolved at work in order to promote job satisfaction among Chinese critical care nurses.

Pietersen (2015) examined job satisfaction among 109 staff nurses in a government hospital in South Africa. He looked at both extrinsic and internal elements that influence work happiness. The work Satisfaction Questionnaire (JSQ), which looked at work satisfaction from a "attitudinal point of view," was used by Pietersen (2015) (p. 22). According to Pietersen's study's findings, the majority of respondents (56%) were unhappy with extrinsic circumstances, and over half of them were unhappy with their jobs. The items with the highest level of discontent were compensation, working conditions, supervisor assistance, and organizational support. The job itself had the highest satisfaction levels, and many respondents thought their work was "worthwhile" and that they loved taking care of their patients (Pietersen, 2015). Research by Gaki et al. (2013), Pietersen (2015), and Ramoo et al. (2013) divided the variables that influence work satisfaction into two categories: intrinsic and extrinsic. The researcher of the current study found the study by El-Jardali et al. (2015) to be significant since it evaluated the essential concepts of work satisfaction and intent to leave. This study benefited from research by Liu et al. (2015), which examined the connections between work satisfaction and desire to leave as well as demographic characteristics and job satisfaction. Despite the fact that the findings of the Liu et al. (2015) study were significant since they offered information to support and develop the current study's ideas. Liu et al. (2015) assessed job satisfaction using the following criteria: control/responsibility; praise/recognition; family/work balance; coworkers; interaction; scheduling; and extrinsic incentives. Numerous variables, including demographic ones, are in line with the researcher's goals for this investigation. The results of this study will broaden our understanding of nursing, indicating that job satisfaction is a significant predictor of nurse retention. Additionally, it will highlight the crucial extrinsic and intrinsic elements that contribute to CCU nurses' job satisfaction. The development of nurse retention initiatives in the CCU, which is essential

in combating the present nursing shortage in this critical care sector, will be aided by factors that contribute to job satisfaction within nursing leadership.

Conceptual Paradigm

The primary focus of this study is on the association of the socio demographic factors, with the perception of the clinical work preparedness and job satisfaction. This association is illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Conceptual Paradigm

The investigator based on reviewed studies and literature operationally covers several socio-demographic factors which could affect the perception of the clinical work preparedness and job satisfaction. These socio-demographic factors include, age, civil status, educational attainment, length of hospital work experiences. Duration of experience in the intensive care unit and the kind of ICU that was allocated.

In addition, this study will look into potential connections between job satisfaction and perceptions of clinical work readiness, specifically with regard to pay, vacation time, workload, work schedule, benefits package, number of weekends off per month, ability to choose shift work, quantity of feedback and encouragement, and career advancement opportunities.

Research Hypotheses

This study has the following hypotheses:

1. There is a significant difference between the perceived clinical work preparedness and the socio-demographic characteristics of the intensive critical care nurses in terms of age, civil status, educational attainment, length of experience in the intensive critical care, length of hospital experience, and type of critical unit.
2. The sociodemographic attributes of critical care nurses, such as age, marital status, level of education, length of experience in intensive critical care, length of hospital stay, and type of critical unit, significantly differ from their perceived job satisfaction.
3. There is a significant relationship between perceived clinical work preparedness and job satisfaction among critical care nurses.

Chapter III

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

To determine if there is a correlation between the level of clinical work preparedness and job satisfaction among critical care nurses in a tertiary hospital in Tabuk, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, a well-laid out research design and methodology is essential. Below provides a detailed description of the methodologies adapted by the researcher in order to answer the research questions.

Research Design

According to Zulueta and Costales (2003), the descriptive technique of research is a fact-finding study with sufficient and correct interpretation of data. It emphasizes describing what is real, such as circumstances, behaviors, conditions, or things that occur right now. Specifically, quantitative research is characterized using statistical analysis. They also explained that there are three basic quantitative research objectives – to describe, to compare and to attribute causality. Numerical values are assigned to variables and the mathematical analysis of these values, such as mean, and the standard deviation are used in the analysis. This study will describe the possible difference of the socio-demographic profile of the intensive critical care nurses (age, civil status, educational attainment, length of experience in the intensive critical care; length of hospital experience; and type of critical unit), their perceived clinical work preparedness and job satisfaction, and significant relationship between their perception of clinical work preparedness and job satisfaction. Level of significance is set at 5%.

The degree of link between two or more variables or sets of scores was measured and described using descriptive correlational research (Creswell, 2014). These research design features are appropriate for the study's primary goals, which include assessing job satisfaction and clinical work readiness as well as figuring out how these variables relate to

one another.

Data were collected through questionnaires. No intervention was introduced to the participants. The variables were examined in their natural environments.

Sampling Procedures

Purposive sampling method was utilized in this study. In this type of non-probability sampling, researchers select the population members who will take part in their survey using their own discretion.

Inclusion Criteria

Only the identified new nurses who pass the probationary period and senior nurses that work in the critical care unit of the tertiary hospital in Tabuk, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia were covered by the study. The nurses must be an employee of the hospital during the period which the study is conducted. They must have the capacity to give consent to participate in the study. Further, they must be willing to answer the three-part questionnaire.

Exclusion Criteria

Critical care nurses who are not anymore connected with the hospital, those who got sick and on leave or off during the conduct of study were excluded from the participation. Those nurses who will not sign the Informed Consent Form were excluded in the study.

Research Setting

In Tabuk, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, a tertiary hospital hosted the study. The target market consists of the intense critical care nurses assigned to the hospital's medical, surgical, neonatal and pediatric, and medical-surgical intensive critical care units. The latter includes cardiac care.

Research Instrument

With permission from the authors, the Casey-Fink Graduate Nurse Experience Survey (2006) from the University of Colorado Hospital was utilized. The three-part instrument used for data gathering is a questionnaire written in the English language. They are employed to collect data more quickly than any other technique. In addition, the intended responders possess literacy skills, so they could easily read and complete the questionnaire.

The instrument has three (3) parts. Part I were used to gather the socio- Demographic characteristics of the critical care nurses (age, civil status, educational attainment, length of experience in the intensive critical care; length of hospital experience; and type of critical unit). The second section of the questionnaire questions about how clinical workers see their level of preparedness for work in terms of abilities and procedure execution, comfort and confidence when completing duties, and challenges adjusting to a new job. The nurses' critical care competency skills requirements and qualification was based on the standard of CBAHI (Central Board for Accreditation of Healthcare Institution).

Part III is on the perceived job satisfaction of the intensive critical care nurses particularly on the areas of salary, vacation, workload, work schedule, benefits package, weekends off per month, opportunity to choose shifts work, amount of encouragement and feedback, and opportunities for career advancement.

The five sections of the Casey-Fink Graduate Nurse Experience Survey are: demographic data; skills/procedure performance (11 items asking respondents to rank their most valuable nursing intensive critical care skills); comfort/confidence (25 items with Likert scale responses, 1 = strongly disagree and 4 = strongly agree); four open-ended questions regarding work environment and challenges in transitioning roles; and nine items on job satisfaction dimensions (with Likert scale responses, 1 = very dissatisfied and 5 = very satisfied). The instrument takes fifteen to twenty minutes to finish.

The ranking of skills/procedure performance was based on the specific skills expected specifically from a nurse intensive critical care. This was based on the standard performance of the nurse in intensive critical care.

The interpretation key used to classify the average level of agreement for each statement:

Scale	Rating Scale	Verbal Description
1	Extreme Difficulty	Slightly Prepared
2	Moderate Difficult	Moderately Prepared
3	Slight Difficulty	Extremely Prepared

The interpretation key used to classify the average level of agreement for each statement:

Scale	Rating Scale	Verbal Description
4	3.25 to 4.00	Strongly Agree/ Highly Comfortable and Confident
3	2.51 to 3.25	Agree/ Moderately Comfortable and Confident
2	1.76 to 2.50	Disagree/ Moderately Uncomfortable and Unconfident
1	1.00 to 1.75	Strongly Disagree/ Highly Uncomfortable and Unconfident

The interpretation key used to classify the average level of agreement for each statement:

Scale	Rating Scale	Verbal Description
5	4.21 to 5.00	Very Satisfied

4	3.41 to 4.20	Moderately Satisfied
3	2.61 to 3.40	Neither Satisfied nor Dissatisfied
2	1.81 to 2.60	Moderately Dissatisfied
1	1.00 to 1.80	Very Dissatisfied

Data Gathering Procedure

Letter of requests was sent to the hospital administrator to seek permission to conduct the study and to request for the list of the names of the critical care nurses (see Appendix A). Upon approval from the Ethics Review Board Committee, through a fully filled-up form, a letter of invitation to target respondents was sent (see Appendix B). The researcher also sent an email request to the author for permission on the adoption of the tool in clinical work preparedness and job satisfaction (see Appendix C).

Data Gathering Procedures

Step 1. The researcher coordinated with the administrator of the hospital.

Step 2. List from the human resource department of the hospital were screened on their eligibility for the study.

Step 3. The researcher individually invited those who qualified to take part in the study.

Step 4. The study's specifics were thoroughly explained to the critical care nurses. They had a chance to ask questions as the explanation was being provided.

Step 5. The informed consent form was signed by the nurses who voluntarily chose to take part.

Step 6. The study's questionnaires were given to the participants to fill out.

Step 7. Throughout the process of gathering the data, a journal of actions was kept.

Step 8. After the surveys were completed, their completeness was assessed.

Step 9. The researcher individually thanked each participant for taking part in the study.

Validity and Reliability of the Tool

The investigator adopted the validated and reliable tool of The Casey Fink Graduate Nurse Experience Survey (2006).

The investigator conducted the pretest to 20 critical care nurses of another hospital who have similar characteristics with the target respondents. Pre-testing was done to assess whether the survey questionnaire has captured the responses that were expected to be collected. Pre-testing was needed to clarify whether the questionnaire was easy to understand and if further changes in the questionnaire were necessary. Reliability Analysis was then conducted to determine whether the scales or test items used in the questionnaire consistently reflect the construct it is measuring. The computed Cronbach's alpha indicates the internal consistency of a set of scales or test items.

The instrument on Level of Comfort and Confidence (Part IIB) has twenty-four (24) scale items that aims to evaluate the perceived level of comfort and confidence in clinical work, all of which were measured using a four-point scale ranging from 1=Strongly Disagree to 4=Strongly Agree were tested. Cronbach's alpha is 0.875, which indicates a high level of internal consistency for the scale. That is, these 24 items reliably measure the same latent variable, which is the perceived level of comfort and confidence in clinical work.

Figure 2. Data Gathering Procedure

Before the data gathering, the researcher explained to the nurses the purpose of the study and the content of the consent form to become respondents of the study through a common orientation, letter sent through email, and one-on-one talk whichever is convenient to the target respondents. After the nurses have given their consent, the researcher requested them to sign the form as an indication of their approval. After then, the respondents can respond to the survey. To make sure the respondent had addressed every question, the researcher examined the completed questionnaire.

All of the respondents' questionnaires were collected by the researcher for processing and encoding. The data were analyzed, followed by research report preparation. The budgetary requirements are also in the Appendices.

Statistical Design

The data in the study were subjected to descriptive and inferential analysis. Data were described in frequency counts, percentage, rank, means, and standard deviations in determining the perception of the intensive critical care nurses of their clinical work

preparedness. Inferential analyses were done using the non-parametric statistical tools like Chi-square test for comparison between 2 groups; and Spearman's rho in determining non-parametric correlations between clinical work preparedness and job satisfaction with the socio-demographic characteristics and the possible relationship between clinical work preparedness and job satisfaction of the nurses. Level of significance is set at 0.05.

Data were processed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 22.

Ethical Considerations

The consent and approval of the ethical review board of University of the Philippines Open University (UPOU) and the participating hospital where the study will be conducted were sought before the beginning of the study. During the course of the inquiry, UPOU's protocol and standards as well as the facilities' ethical review boards were followed. After clearance, the study's results were gathered between March and May of 2022. Collection periods were ended early because the necessary quantity of samples was obtained.

In addition, permission to use, copy, translate and/or modify the measurement tools Casey-Fink Graduate Nurse Experience Survey (2006) questionnaire were secured before the start of data collection.

Protection and safety of all human subjects were provided and maintained throughout the course of the study. All target respondents received a letter of invitation to become a respondent of the study together with a copy of the Informed Consent Form for them to read and sign. The purpose of the study was stated so they will have a basis in their decision to be or not to become part of the study.

They received guarantees that any information they provided would be kept private and utilized only for the study's objectives. They might not face consequences if they choose to

discontinue participating throughout the data gathering process.

The participants were informed of their protection from any form of potential emotional, psychological, or physical risk. They were protected from invasion of their privacy and the preservation of their personal dignity.

The names of the respondents were coded using alphanumeric in the encoding of the responses. The computer unit used for encoding and the files where the raw data were encoded have a password where the researcher has the sole access. The processed data was stored in a non-writable disc.

The data collected for the study were discarded 6 months after its completion. The hard copies were shredded, and the soft copies were deleted having the representative from the UP Open University as witness.

Copies of the final research report were provided to the University of the Philippines Open University, the tertiary hospital in Tabuk, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia for possible publication in a peer-reviewed journal and were presented in nursing conferences or conventions where the results of the study could be most useful. Names and identities of the respondents were not mentioned in the study.

Table 1

Statistical Design Matrix

Objective	Variables	Level of Measurement	Statistical Test
<p>Objective 1: To determine the level of clinical work preparedness of the critical care nurses in terms of:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Skills and Procedure Performance 2. Comfort and Confidence 3. Work Environment and Difficulty of Role Transition 	<p>Skills/ Procedures – Ordinal Individual MLQ Questions</p>	<p>Ratio Interval</p>	<p>Mean and Standard Deviation</p>
<p>Objective 2: To determine the level of job satisfaction of the critical care nurses in terms of:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Salary 2. Vacation 3. Workload 4. Work Schedule 5. Benefits Package 6. Weekends off per month 7. Opportunity to choose shifts work 8. Amount of encouragement and feedback 9. Opportunities for Career Advancement 	<p>Area of Job Satisfaction Scores QWI Factor Scores</p>	<p>Interval Ratio</p>	<p>Mean and Standard Deviation</p>
<p>Objective 3: To determine the relationship between the level of clinical work preparedness and the socio-demographic characteristics of the critical care nurses.</p>	<p>Skills/Procedures Comfort and Confidence Transition and Work Environment Demographic Profile</p>	<p>Ordinal Interval Nominal Nominal/Ordinal</p>	<p>Chi-Square Test</p>

Objective 4:

To determine the relationship between the job satisfaction and the socio demographic characteristics of the critical care nurses.

Area of Job Satisfaction

Scores

Demographic

Profile

Interval

Nominal/Ordinal

Chi-Square Test

Objective 5:

To determine the relationship between the level of clinical work preparedness and the job satisfaction of the critical care nurses.

Clinical Work Preparedness

Job Satisfaction

Nominal/Ratio

Ratio

Spearman rho Correlation and Chi-Square test of association

Chapter IV

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This chapter presents and discusses the findings and analysis of the study. The first part of this chapter presents the findings according to selected demographic variables. Subsequently, the analysis is presented and arranged according to the objectives of the study.

Socio-Demographic Profile (n = 149)

Table 2
Socio-Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage
Age		
30 years old and below	51	34.2
31-40 years old	87	58.4
41 years old and older	11	7.4
Civil Status		
Single	59	39.6
Married	89	59.7
Widow	1	0.7
Education Attainment		
Diploma	5	3.4
BSN	144	96.6
Masters	0	0
Length of Intensive Critical Care Experience		
Less than 5 years	39	26.2
5 – 10 years	90	60.4
Greater than 10 years	20	13.4
Length of Hospital Work Experience		
Less than 5 years	35	23.5
5 – 10 years	77	51.7

	Greater than 10 years	37	24.5
Unit	Type of Intensive Critical Care		
	Medical, including coronary care	31	20.8
	Surgical, including trauma and cardiovascular	10	6.7
	Neonatal and Pediatric	72	48.3
	Medical-surgical	36	24.2
Hospital Ownership	Government	149	100
	Private	0	0

There were 149 respondents in this study with age group below 30 years old and above. More than half of the respondents are between 31-40 years group (58.4%), majority were married at 59.7%, majority are BSN graduate (96.6%), with 5-10 years hospital work experience (51.7), with length experience in the Intensive Critical Care Unit (60.4%), mostly assigned at the Neonatal and Pediatric division (48.3%).

The purpose of this study was to identify the variables that are related to critical care nurses' levels of job satisfaction and clinical work readiness at a tertiary hospital in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. The results were presented according to the highest score obtained per dimension.

Table 3 shows the level of clinical preparedness in terms of skills and procedure performance.

Table 3

Level of Clinical Preparedness in terms of Skills and Procedure Performance

Skills and Procedures	Extreme Difficulty		Moderate Difficulty		Slight Difficulty	
	n	%	n	%	n	%
Functions in accordance with legislation, common laws, organizational regulations, and by-laws which affect nursing practice.	63	42.3	9	6.0	2	1.3
Provides care to meet individual patient needs on a 24-hour basis.	7	4.7	37	24.8	3	2.0
Practices current critical care nursing competently.	13	8.7	3	2.0	4	2.7
Delivers nursing care in a way that can be ethically justified.	31	20.8	11	7.4	5	3.4
Demonstrates accountability for his/her professional judgment and actions.	10	6.7	25	16.8	4	2.7

Creates and maintains an environment which promotes safety and security of patients, visitors, and staff.	11	7.4	21	14.1	14	9.4
Masters the use of all essential equipment, available services, and supplies for immediate care of patients.	8	5.4	5	3.4	8	5.4
Protects the patients from developing environmental induced infection.	1	.7	27	18.1	47	31.5
Utilizes the nursing process in an explicit systematic manner to achieve the goals of care.	2	1.3	2	1.3	44	29.5
Carries out health education for promotion and maintenance of health.	1	.7	4	2.7	13	8.7
Acts to enhance the professional development of self and others.	0	0	1	.7	3	2.0
I am independent in all skills.	2	1.3	4	2.7	2	1.3

The top three skills and procedures that the most nurses ranked as extremely difficult or slightly prepared are operates in compliance with organizational, common, and legislative regulations and bylaws that impact nursing practice (42.3%), provides nursing care in a manner that is morally justifiable (20.8%), and establishes and maintains a setting that fosters patient, visitor, and staff safety and security (7.4%).

This indicates that most nurses feel very uncomfortable doing these tasks independently. It is to note that more than 40% of the respondents perceive that tasks related to legislation, common laws, organizational regulations, and by-laws in nursing practice are extremely difficult to do by themselves.

Additionally, the majority of nurses ranked the following three skills and procedures as being either moderately difficult or moderately prepared to perform: demonstrates accountability for one's professional judgment and actions (16.8%), protects patients from developing environmental-induced infections (18.1%), and provides care to meet individual patient needs on a 24-hour basis (24.8%).

The procedure with almost one-fourth of the respondents believing to be moderately difficult to do independently is providing care to meet a patient's needs on a 24-hour basis. Finally, protecting patients from environmental infections (31.5%), using the nursing process

in an explicit, systematic manner to achieve goals (29.5%), and creating and maintaining an environment that promotes patient, visitor, and staff safety and security are the top three skills and procedures that most nurses ranked as being slightly difficult (9.4%).

This indicates that most nurses feel very uncomfortable in doing the tasks independently. It can be noted that more than 40% of the respondents perceive tasks related to legislation, common laws, organizational regulations, and by-laws in nursing practice as extremely difficult to do by themselves.

This to note that nurses are not doing independent nursing intervention in the institution without the physician's order. Moreover, critical care nurses are afraid to commit mistakes related organization laws and regulations. In which, there must be action, or a deliberative nursing intervention based on their critical judgment as supported by recent studies. This is consistent on the work of Ida Jean Orlando and her Deliberative Nursing Process Theory. One of the earliest nursing theorists to create a nursing process theory was Ida Jean Orlando, who did so by using her own analysis and research. She founded the Deliberative Nursing Process Theory, which emphasizes communication between the patient and the nurse. The nurse's goal is aimed at improving the patient's immediate situation by relieving stress or discomfort and with effective communication, create a positive nurse-patient relationship. Deliberative nursing process allow a nurse to formulate a nursing care plan that can easily be adapted in care a problem arise in a complex situation. Also, in Deliberative Nursing Process theory, patient validate the nursing intervention by effective nurse-patient interaction.

Furthermore, nurses are not allowed to discuss patient's general condition to the folks, only the attending physician or consultant has the authority to do the task. There is also language barrier as some of nurses in critical area are not Arabic speaking, thus, interpreter is needed by every institution to improve the services in terms of communication gap as well

to validate the nursing care rendered.

This is in line with the requirements of Article VI of the Philippines Nurses Act of 2002 (RA No. 9173), which states that it is a nurse's responsibility to respect the standards of safe nursing practice and adhere to the code of ethics. As long as the setting is one that encourages patient safety, there are many ways to provide nursing care.

Table 4 shows the level of clinical preparedness in terms of comfort and confidence.

Table 4
Level of Clinical Preparedness in terms Comfort and Confidence

Statements	Mean Score	Standard Deviation
I feel confident communicating with physicians.	3.26	.471
I am comfortable knowing what to do for a dying patient.	3.23	.495
I feel comfortable delegating tasks to the Nursing Assistant.	3.16	.570
I feel at ease asking for help from other RNs on the unit.	3.21	.536
I am having difficulty prioritizing patient care needs.	2.40	.813
I feel my preceptor provides encouragement and feedback about my work.	3.05	.490
I feel staff is available to me during new situations and procedures.	2.83	.623
I feel overwhelmed by my patient care responsibilities and workload.	2.79	.671
I feel supported by the nurses on my unit.	3.17	.476
I have opportunities to practice skills and procedures more than once.	3.19	.409
I feel comfortable communicating with patients and their families.	3.03	.550
I am able to complete my patient care assignment on time.	3.13	.414
I feel the expectations of me in this job are realistic.	2.97	.418
I feel prepared to complete my job responsibilities.	3.07	.430
I feel comfortable making suggestions for changes to the nursing plan of care.	2.85	.586
I am having difficulty organizing patient care needs.	2.38	.703
I feel I may harm a patient due to my lack of knowledge and experience.	2.44	.791
There are positive role models for me to observe on my unit.	2.99	.526
My preceptor is helping me to develop confidence in my practice.	3.13	.469
I am supported by my family/friends.	3.21	.523
I am satisfied with my chosen nursing specialty.	3.17	.499
I feel my work is exciting and challenging.	3.18	.451
I feel my manager provides encouragement and feedback about my work.	3.03	.725
I am experiencing stress in my personal life.	3.05	.602
Overall Mean	2.97	.234

In terms of comfort and confidence, the higher scores correspond to high agreement on the respective statement. The overall mean (2.97) indicates that the nurses are moderately comfortable and confident in their work. On average, the mean scores show moderate agreement which indicates that the nurses generally agree with the statements and are moderately comfortable and confident with regards to clinical work.

It is to note that the nurses feel very confident in communicating with physicians as their mean score is 3.26 (strongly agree). A limited variety in the respondents' scores is shown by the modest standard deviation.

However, nurses disagree with negatively worded statements. I am having difficulty prioritizing patient care need, I feel I may harm a patient due to my lack of knowledge and experience. The majority of nurses who disagree with the aforementioned claims are still at ease and self-assured when it comes to setting priorities, planning patient care, and ensuring that a patient is not harmed by their inexperience. A limited variety in the respondents' scores is shown by the modest standard deviation.

Nurses must possess strong communication skills to be able to receive and exchange information, especially those who provide end of life care to patients and their families.

This is a fundamental nursing skill that all medical professionals must have in order to be truly successful. Additionally, a customized strategy must be considered to fulfill each patient's particular communication needs, particularly in cases when the patient may be in pain or disturbed. Additionally, nurses need to feel at ease starting or participating in discussions about the end-of-life process.

An average that critical care nurses are confident in dealing with dying patient in intensive critical care unit and confident in communicating with the physician.

difficulty of transition.

Table 5

Level of Clinical Preparedness in terms work environment and difficulty of transition

Work Environment and Difficulty of Role Transition	Frequency	Percentage
What difficulties, if any, are you currently experiencing with the transition from the other hospital units to the intensive critical care unit?		
Role Expectations	64	43
Lack of Confidence	24	16.1
Workload	44	29.5
Fears	8	5.4
Orientation Issues	5	3.4
Others	4	2.7
What could be done to help you feel more supported or integrated into the unit?		
Improved Orientation	58	38.9
Increased Support	31	20.8
Unit Socialization	10	6.7
Improved Work Environment	50	33.6
Others	0	0
What aspects of your work environment are most satisfying?		
Peer Support	88	59.1
Patients and Families	12	8.1
Ongoing Learning	13	8.7
Professional Nursing Role	16	10.7
Positive Work Environment	19	12.8
Others	1	0.7
What aspects of your work environment are least satisfying?		
Nursing Work Environment	61	40.9
System	37	24.8
Interpersonal Relationships	43	28.9
Orientation	5	3.4
Others	3	2.0

Four multiple-choice questions concerning the work environment of nurses and challenges in transitioning between roles were posed to the participants.

The first question asks the respondents whether they are currently experiencing any difficulties in their transition from other hospital units to the intensive critical care unit. Sixty-four (or 43% percent) of the respondents answered their role expectations and had the highest frequency among the other choices. This was followed by their workload at 29.5% and lack of confidence (16.1%).

This means that the nurses may have difficulty in adjusting to their work environment due to their new roles, workloads, and lack of confidence. In agreement with the study *Clinical Work Preparedness and Job Satisfaction among Critical Care Nurses..*

conducted by Oshodi, et al (2019) which revealed that they are greatly challenged when they are tasked with dual duty, coordinating, and simultaneously looking after patients. Quality health care is not provided and hinders the provision of quality patient care.

This is not only relevant to the institution but worldwide as the workload and staffing shortage is a global issue. Thus, evaluation of staffing and scheduling is a regular stint. During the COVID-19 pandemic, there were always staff shortage as some staff were suspected and confirmed positive and must undergo quarantine for 14-21 days. The option was a 12- hour shifting instead of 8 hours, to limit hospital exposure at the same time to cover the deficit of staffing. The Ministry of Health of Saudi Arabia has given financial aid to those nurses working in intensive critical care unit.

Furthermore, the institution adopted flexible staffing methods to meet the patient needs, as well as enhancement of the staff and organization goals to provide excellent services. The vacation for non-Saudi staff was put on hold during the pandemic due to the closure of travel destinations and other rigid.

The second question is about ways on how to make the nurses feel more supported or integrated into the intensive critical care unit. 38.9% or 58 of the respondents answered Improved Orientation. This was followed by Improved Work Environment (33.6%) and Increased Support (20.8%). This means that the nurses feel that with an improved and updated orientation, suitable work environment, and increased support from the colleagues, they have an easier transition into the unit.

With these findings, the researchers' formulated a unit orientation manual, to enhance the knowledge and skills of critical care nurses. The newly hired staff has been given a preceptor to supervise them. In-service lectures were conducted on a weekly basis. In-depth training on Basic Life support, Advanced Life Support, Neonatal Resuscitation Program and Pediatric Advance Life Support became a prerequisite to work in the ICU's and a renewable requirement every 2 years. There are trainings and seminars conducted in the hospital as

required by Ministry of Health, necessary in order to provide quality care and patient's safety. Like in the Neonatal Individualized Developmental Care Program, a training was initiated by MOH and STABLE course. The PICC line insertion training among Neonatal Intensive Care Nurses were then formulated after the researcher finished her intensive training from King Faisal Specialist Hospital NICU educator and which was practiced by the critical care unit from 2019 up to the present. In the year 2020-2021, the researcher conducted seminar and hands-on training for PICC line insertion of the NICU senior staff. At present, it was successfully implemented as many PICC line as part of NICU management especially for extreme preterm neonates and critically ill who needed long term treatment with TPN and inotropes, with very good outcome. The researcher being a nurse manager initiated a Daily Safety Huddle to discuss any issues of concerns that occur for the last 24 hours, to do corrective actions immediately. To improve critical care, a regular meeting on Morbidity and Mortality to discuss the issues and create recommendations. Furthermore, the researcher initiated the NICU service indicators to monitor and evaluate the different services, such as hand hygiene compliance, staff essential training record, nursing documentation, blood transfusion compliance, incidence of pressure sore, incidence of fall and incidence of needle stick injury since 2017 until today. At present, the researcher is working on quality improvement project to lessen the length of stay and decrease the mortality of NICU patient in collaboration with NICU physician.

The results of Azimian et al. (2014), which showed that nurses' ability to adjust to change is significantly influenced by their perception of support, provide credence to this. Burnout and unhappiness at work are linked to inadequate support for nurses during transition. Additionally, Dyess and Parker (2012) noted that educational assistance improved nurses' professional abilities, ability to stay in the field, and ability to adjust to change. Nurses can manage change by giving them various forms of support, particularly from their peers.

The third question is regarding aspects of the nurses' work environment that they are

most satisfied in. 59.1% or more than half of the respondents answered Peer Support. This indicates that the nurses are most satisfied about the support they receive from their colleagues. This was then followed by Positive Work Environment (12.8%) and Professional Nursing Role (10.7%). Given that the critical care nurses in our hospital are international, conflict is often characterized as internal or external strife resulting from differences in views, beliefs, or sentiments. Lack of resources, reorganization, and unclear position expectations are all common causes of conflict. This finding suggests that a leader's job is to foster an atmosphere in the workplace where conflict may be used to foster development, creativity, and efficiency. wherever possible, looks for win-win solutions to conflicts. increases persuasiveness and open communication by using assertive communication techniques.

Lastly, the fourth question asks the respondents the aspects of their work environment that they are least satisfied with 40.9% of the respondents answered their nursing work environment indicating that their work environment needs to be improved on. This was followed by Interpersonal Relationships (28.9%) and Work System (24.8%).

The researcher conducted unit monthly meeting and departmental monthly meeting to create a positive work environment. According to Brandt's (1994) interactive leadership model, leaders who value and empower their followers may create an environment at work that encourages autonomy and innovation. This leadership encourages people to contribute their special abilities toward a shared objective by recognizing each person's individuality.

The study of Carvello (2011) revealed that the need to receive support from colleagues is an intervention of strong emotional support as widely recognized by half of the participants.

Table 6 shows the level of job satisfaction among critical care nurses.

Table 6
Level of Job Satisfaction among Critical Care Nurses

Area of Job Satisfaction	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal
Salary	3.16	.881	Neutral
Vacation	2.44	.925	Moderately Satisfied
Benefits package	3.12	.993	Neutral
Hours that you work	3.09	.975	Neutral
Weekends off per month	3.04	1.04	Neutral
Your amount of responsibility	3.12	1.04	Neutral
Opportunities for career advancement	3.15	.950	Neutral
Amount of encouragement and feedback	3.15	.950	Neutral
Opportunity to choose shifts work	3.10	1.04	Neutral

The nurses were asked how satisfied they were per area of job satisfaction. On the average, critical care nurses were satisfied or dissatisfied with their salary (3.16); opportunities for career advancement (3.15); amount of encouragement and feedback (3.15); benefits package (3.12); amount of responsibility (3.12) opportunity to choose shift work (3.10), hours that you work (3.09); weekends off per month (3.04) and vacation (2.44).

The areas with the lowest levels of satisfaction were leadership, prospects for advancement, engagement in decision-making, degree of trust and praise, and pay level. The areas with the highest levels of satisfaction were colleague and job satisfaction.

Sveinsdottir (2015) found similar results, indicating that nurses were least happy with their possibilities for advancement and pay level and most content with their head nurses and fellow nurses. Pay level was shown to be the second most significant factor influencing job satisfaction among nursing professionals working in Slovenian hospitals. It was discovered that hospitals' efforts to increase nurses' job satisfaction are constrained by the wage factor, which is independent of organizational structure.

Critical care nurses are significantly dissatisfied with their salary as the lowest satisfaction score and moderately satisfied with the vacation. Nurses in critical care unit is exposed to several stressful situation especially dealing with patient who is terminally ill and dying thus, vacation is one way of distressing in a strenuous situation, which is evident in this study. In which vacation is the most satisfying among the listed choices of job. The

researcher as a nurse manager made a vacation plan for the whole year period and approves emergency leave if staff need it, in which schedule is adjusted according to unit needs. Furthermore, request of duty and week- ends off are distributed among staff with valid reasons. The researcher as a nurse manager based on the above findings of satisfaction that vacation is the most satisfying aspects of job among critical care nurses have distributed request for prefer vacation date before forwarded to nursing office for approval. Vacation plan is made in accordance with the nursing administration policy.

Table 7 shows the relationship between the level of clinical work preparedness and the socio-demographic characteristics of the critical care nurses.

Table 7

Chi-square tests between the level of clinical work preparedness and the socio-demographic characteristics

	Age		Civil Status		Educational Attainment		Length of ICU Exp.		Length of Hosp. Exp.		Type of ICU	
	χ^2	p-value	χ^2	p-value	χ^2	p-value	χ^2	p-value	χ^2	p-value	χ^2	p-value
Skills and Procedure Performance												
Extreme Difficulty	37.26	.011	13.55	.852	2.95	.982	33.82	.027	100.38	<.001	92.88	<.001
Moderate Difficulty	36.85	.025	32.98	.062	18.81	.065	52.83	<.001	108.35	<.001	155.76	<.001
Slight Difficulty	30.61	.105	44.48	.003	24.90	.009	42.70	.005	91.25	<.001	120.45	<.001
Comfort and Confidence												
Overall Comfort and Confidence	41.31	.588	62.52	.034	48.36	.001	60.02	.054	102.14	.003	128.51	<.001
Work environment and difficulty of role transition												
Difficulties with transitioning from other hospital units to ICU	26.99	.003	6.04	.812	7.27	.202	18.54	.046	26.41	.034	33.46	.004
Support and Integration into the Unit	8.63	.195	23.46	.001	1.22	.748	20.41	.002	47.88	<.001	46.47	<.001
Satisfaction in the Work Environment	15.61	.112	29.62	.001	3.587	.610	13.56	.194	39.27	.001	31.41	.008
Unsatisfaction in the Work Environment	23.93	.002	16.62	.034	4.35	.361	16.67	.034	33.04	.001	60.32	<.001

*p-values less than 0.05 are considered significant

The correlation between two category variables was ascertained using the chi-square test. The strong correlation between the critical care nurses' sociodemographic traits and their level of clinical job readiness was also determined using this method.

At 5% level of significance, there is sufficient evidence to conclude that with regards to Skills and Procedure Performance, Skills of Extreme Difficulty have a significant relationship with the nurses' age, length of intensive critical care unit (ICCU) experience, length of hospital experience, and type of ICCU.

This indicates that the age group of the nurses, how long they have been working in the hospital and ICCU, and the type of ICCU that they worked in have a significant effect on which skills they rank as extremely difficult.

In an article published by Nursing News (2022), younger nurses referred to as millennial enjoy rapid change and is adaptable to new locations, high pressured, frenetic hospital environment. Millennial nurses are good at handling several tasks and thrive in demanding environments. They also adjust well to changing conditions. Compared to senior nurses, younger nurses could select a skill or treatment that they believe to be more challenging.

Also, at 5% level of significance, there is a significant relationship between the skills the nurses' ranked as moderately difficult with their age, length of hospital work experience, and type of ICCU they worked in. This means that the nurses' age, how long they have been working in the hospital and ICCU, and the type of ICCU that they worked in have a significant effect on which skills they rank as moderately difficult. This means the older the nurse, the more years of experience gained and perceived as slightly difficult or extreme clinically prepared to work in critical care unit.

In order to assist new nurses cope with the harsh reality of the job, veteran and experienced nurses should be available to provide appropriate debriefing and emotional support. Nurses who more experience working in a hospital may rank a different skill as moderately difficult compared to those nurses who have less experience.

There is also sufficient evidence to conclude that the skills the nurses' ranked as slightly difficult have a significant relationship with their civil status, educational attainment,

and length of hospital and ICCU experience.

Nurses who are married may rank a different skill as moderately difficult compared to those nurses who are single. Therefore, nurses who is matured or experienced, married, having longer years of ICCU experience and type of ICCU they work have significant effect of the clinical work preparedness. Overall, the socio-demographic characteristics varies among critical care nurses' perception on the ranking of clinically prepared.

Studies on female labor have consistently found lower employment participation rates, especially when the worker is married (Shields, 2004). Employers are more interested in young people on the demand side as long as they are dependable and easily accessible.

At 5% level of significance, there is sufficient evidence to conclude that with regards to Comfort and Confidence, the nurses' overall comfort and confidence scores have a significant relationship with the nurses' civil status, educational attainment, length of hospital length experience and type of ICCU they worked on.

This indicates that the overall comfort and confidence scores of the nurses are significantly influenced by their civil status, level of education, length of hospital employment, and kind of intensive care unit (ICCU). This indicates that the nurses working in a specific type of ICCU may have a different mean score compared to nurses working in another type of ICCU.

At 5% level of significance, there is sufficient evidence to conclude that with regards to Work Environment and Difficulty of Role Transition, the nurses' type of difficult experience in transitioning into ICCU have a significant relationship with the nurses' age, length of intensive critical care unit experience, length of hospital experience, and type of ICCU. Furthermore, successful leaders have a vision and strategy for the future. Building an efficient team and allocating talent are critical skills.

This indicates that the age group of the nurses, how long they have been working in the

hospital and ICCU, and the type of ICCU that they worked in have a significant effect on which type of difficulty they may have experience when transitioning to the intensive critical care unit.

Nurses with less experience working in the ICCU may choose *lack of confidence* as the type of difficulty they experience when transitioning to the ICCU while nurses with more experience may choose a different type.

There is also enough data to draw the conclusion that the nurses' decision on how best to help them feel supported and integrated into the unit is significantly influenced by their marital status, the length of time they have worked in the ICCU and hospital, and the nature of the ICCU.

This means that the marital status of the nurses, how long they have been working in the hospital and ICCU, and the type of ICCU that they worked in have a significant effect on what aspect of their work environment that needs to be improved on for them to feel supported and integrated into the unit.

There is also a significant relationship between the nurses' choice on which aspect of their work environment that they are most satisfied about and the civil status, length of hospital experience and type of ICCU they worked in.

This indicates that the marital status of the nurses, how long they have been working in the hospital and the type of ICCU that they worked in have a significant effect on what aspect of their work environment that they are most satisfied about.

Lastly, there is also a significant relationship between the nurses' choice on which aspect of their work environment that they are most unsatisfied about and their age, civil status, length of hospital and ICCU experience and type of ICCU they worked on.

Overall, this indicates that the marital status of the nurses, how long they have been working in the hospital and ICCU, and the type of ICCU that they worked in have a significant

effect on what aspect of their work environment that they are most unsatisfied about. Thus, the critical care nurses' perspective of clinical preparedness with the socio-demographic characteristics varies. The result shows age, civil status, the length of hospital and unit experience accentuated with the maturity or seniority. Studies have shown that there is a correlation between emotional intelligence and positive patient outcomes. This means married nurses may rank a different scale compared to those nurses who are single.

This is evident in my unit, nurses who are older and work longer appear to be more organized and efficient when it comes to time management and have positive outcome. Daily safety huddle poster learning as well addressing immediately some issues will provide quality services and patient's safety.

Table 8 shows the result of the Chi-square between job satisfaction and the socio-demographic characteristics of the critical care nurses with their corresponding p-values.

Table 8

Results of each Chi-square test between job satisfaction and the socio-demographic characteristics of the critical care nurses with their corresponding p-values

	Age		Civil Status		Educational Attainment		Length of ICU Exp.		Length of Hosp. Exp.		Type of ICU	
	χ^2	P-value	χ^2	P-value	χ^2	P-value	χ^2	P-value	χ^2	P-value	χ^2	P-value
Salary	31.50	<.001	7.42	.492	7.03	.135	31.02	<.001	32.67	.001	43.13	<.001
Vacation	17.05	.030	4.14	.844	5.48	.241	14.23	.076	36.72	<.001	40.45	<.001
Benefits package	25.05	<.001	7.14	.308	3.73	.292	21.09	.002	24.42	.004	39.47	<.001
Hours that you work	18.68	.017	3.35	.911	12.49	.014	14.33	.074	21.60	.042	26.52	.009
Weekends off per month	21.25	.007	5.16	.740	5.21	.266	18.31	.019	23.02	.028	46.71	<.001
Your amount of responsibility	20.63	.008	7.50	.484	7.75	.101	8.36	.399	20.23	.063	49.51	<.001
Opportunities for career advancement	17.51	.064	8.75	.556	8.085	.152	15.32	.121	23.71	.070	42.54	<.001
Amount of encouragement and feedback	21.36	.006	9.075	.336	9.10	.059	28.89	<.001	34.45	.001	27.18	.007
Opportunity to choose shifts work	31.67	<.001	6.44	.598	12.49	.014	24.55	.002	28.12	.005	32.57	.001
Overall Satisfaction	46.16	.549	37.11	.873	18.00	.803	75.10	.007	137.74	<.001	89.30	.082

At 5% level of significance, there is sufficient evidence to conclude that with regards to Areas of Job Satisfaction, *Salary* has a significant relationship with the nurses' age, length of intensive critical care unit (ICCU) experience, length of hospital experience, and type of ICU. This indicates that the age group of the nurses, how long they have been working in the hospital and ICU, and the type of ICU that they worked in have a significant effect on their salary satisfaction scores.

This indicates that changes in the nurses' wage satisfaction levels, whether positive or

negative, are significantly influenced by the aforementioned demographics. For example, younger nurses may have a different (higher/lower) salary satisfaction score (may be more satisfied or not) compared to older nurses. Meaning, the older the staff nurses with long service of work affects her perception on job satisfaction compare the younger respondents.

Also, at 5% level of significance, there is a significant relationship between the *Vacation* satisfaction score with the nurses' age, length of hospital work experience, and type of ICCU they worked in.

This means that the nurses' age, how long they have been working in the hospital, and the type of ICCU that they worked in have a significant effect on their vacation satisfaction score. Meaning nurses who have more experience working in a hospital may be less satisfied on their vacation leaves compared to those nurses who have less experience.

At 5% level of significance, there is a significant relationship between the nurses' *Benefits* satisfaction score with their age, length of hospital and ICCU work experience, and type of ICCU they worked in.

This means that the nurses' age, how long they have been working in the hospital and ICCU, and the type of ICCU that they worked in have a significant effect on their benefits satisfaction score.

Meaning, nurses who have more experience working in an intensive critical care unit may be less satisfied on their benefits packages compared to those nurses who have less experience.

At 5% level of significance, there is a significant relationship between the nurses' *Hours that they work* satisfaction score with their age, educational attainment, length of hospital work experience, and type of ICCU they worked in. This means that the nurses' age, education, how long they have been working in the hospital, and the type of ICCU that they worked in have a significant effect on their work hours satisfaction score. For

example, older nurses may be more/less satisfied on their work hours compared to younger nurses.

At 5% level of significance, there is a significant relationship between the nurses' *Weekends off per month* satisfaction score with their age, length of hospital and ICCU work experience, and type of ICCU they worked in.

This means that the nurses' age, how long they have been working in the hospital and ICCU, and the type of ICCU that they worked in have a significant effect on their weekends off per month satisfaction score. For example, nurses working in one type of ICCU may be more/less satisfied on the number of weekends off they have per month compared to nurses working in another ICCU.

At 5% level of significance, there is a significant relationship between the nurses' *Amount of Responsibility* satisfaction score with their age and type of ICCU they worked in. This means that the nurses' age and the type of ICCU that they worked in have a significant effect on their responsibility satisfaction score. For example, nurses working in one type of ICCU may be more/less satisfied on their responsibility load compared to nurses working in another ICCU.

At 5% level of significance, there is a significant relationship between the nurses' *Opportunities for career advancement* satisfaction score with their type of ICCU they worked in. This means that the type of ICCU that they worked in have a significant effect on their opportunities for career advancement satisfaction score. For example, nurses working in one type of ICCU may be more/less satisfied on their career advancement opportunity compared to nurses working in another ICCU.

At 5% level of significance, there is a significant relationship between the nurses' *Amount of encouragement and feedback* satisfaction score with their age, length of hospital and ICCU work experience, type of ICCU they worked in. This means that the nurses' age, how long they have been working in the hospital and ICCU, and the type of ICCU that they

worked in have a significant effect on their amount of encouragement and feedback satisfaction score. For example, nurses working in one type of ICCU may be more/less satisfied on the amount of support they receive compared to nurses working in another ICCU.

At 5% level of significance, there is a significant relationship between the nurses' *Opportunities to choose shifts work* satisfaction score with their age, educational attainment, length of hospital and ICCU work experience, type of ICCU they worked in. This means that the nurses' age, education, how long they have been working in the hospital and ICCU, and the type of ICCU that they worked in have a significant effect on their opportunities to choose their shifts score. For example, older nurses may be more/less satisfied on how they choose their work schedule compared to younger nurses.

Overall, at 5% level of significance, there is a significant relationship between the nurses' *overall job satisfaction* score with their length of hospital and ICCU work experience. This means that the length they have been working in the hospital and ICCU have a significant effect on their overall satisfaction score.

For example, nurses who more experience working in a hospital may be overall more/less satisfied on their job in general compared to those nurses who have less experience.

Overall, the critical care nurse who is older, work longer in the hospital and in CCU, have less satisfaction in some aspects of their job. The findings may be used to create strategies using performance appraisal to motivate employees especially those nurses working in critical area. Some institutions have programs, like nurses who work night shifts and weekend duty has salary differentials compare to those staff working on regular days. Salary will have to be adjusted according to annual performance review; additional salary increase based on performance. The annual appraisal will be determined the actual developmental needs of the staff as well. Furthermore, the appraiser can be the in charge

or preceptor of a new staff who work directly with the new staff.

To determine if two categorical variables are related, one can use the chi-square test for independence, commonly known as the chi-square test of association. The test determines whether there is an association between categorical variables and is a nonparametric test. This test was performed to see if there was a significant correlation between the critical care nurses' job happiness and their degree of clinical work preparation.

Table 9 shows the results of each Chi-square tests to determine the significant relationship between the level of critical work preparedness and job satisfaction.

Table 9

The results of each Chi-square test with their corresponding p- values

	Extreme Difficulty		Moderate Difficulty		Slight Difficulty		Difficulties with transitioning		Support and Integration into the Unit		Satisfaction in the Work Environment		Unsatisfaction in the Work Environment	
	chi	p-value	chi	p-value	chi	p-value	chi	p-value	chi	p-value	chi	p-value	chi	p-value
Salary	88.31	<.001	111.62	<.001	72.18	.005	51.21	<.001	34.25	.001	59.70	<.001	64.97	<.001
Vacation	150.37	<.001	158.87	<.001	104.81	<.001	52.33	<.001	32.08	.001	27.62	.119	40.94	.001
Workload	42.81	.061	71.27	<.001	80.53	<.001	46.71	<.001	28.67	.001	23.79	.069	41.78	<.001
Work Schedule	158.23	<.001	162.74	<.001	86.33	<.001	41.06	<.001	14.92	.246	38.54	.008	57.21	<.001
Benefits Package	99.93	<.001	125.45	<.001	100.91	<.001	47.97	<.001	15.67	.207	38.41	.008	43.13	<.001
Weekends off per month	73.83	.016	147.09	<.001	152.00	<.001	41.71	.003	27.97	.006	32.63	.037	59.06	<.001
Opportunity to choose shifts work	70.18	.002	132.61	<.001	122.79	<.001	27.87	.314	25.13	.048	24.42	.495	37.105	.011
Amount of encouragement and feedback	85.25	<.001	131.90	<.001	116.73	<.001	56.51	<.001	24.102	.020	29.62	.076	51.41	<.001
Opportunities for career advancement	111.62	<.001	142.01	<.001	85.79	<.001	38.61	.007	.18.06	.114	29.06	.087	40.61	.001
Overall Job Satisfaction	417.64	<.001	361.71	<.001	412.00	<.001	19237	<.001	126.05	<.001	159.41	.009	136.83	.004

**p-values less than 0.05 are considered significant*

At 5% level of significance, there is sufficient evidence to conclude that the nurses' Skills of Extreme Difficulty have a significant relationship with all areas of their job

satisfaction score. This means that each individual area of job satisfaction has a significant effect on what skill/procedure the nurses will rank as extreme difficulty and vice-versa.

At 5% level of significance, there is sufficient evidence to conclude that the nurses' Skills of Moderate Difficulty have a significant relationship with all areas of their job satisfaction score. This means that each individual area of job satisfaction has a significant effect on what skill/procedure the nurses will rank as moderate difficulty and vice-versa.

At 5% level of significance, there is sufficient evidence to conclude that the nurses' Skills of Slight Difficulty have a significant relationship with all areas of their job satisfaction score. This means that each individual area of job satisfaction has a significant effect on what skill/procedure the nurses will rank as slight difficulty and vice-versa.

At 5% level of significance, there is sufficient evidence to conclude that with regards to Work Environment and Difficulty of Role Transition, the nurses' type of difficult experience in transitioning into ICCU have a significant relationship with all areas of their job satisfaction score except for *Opportunity to choose shifts work*. This means that each individual area of job satisfaction has a significant effect on which type of difficulty they may have experience when transitioning to the intensive critical care unit and vice-versa.

There is enough data, at a 5% level of significance, to draw the conclusion that all aspects of the nurses' job satisfaction are significantly impacted by their decision on how best to help and integrate them into the unit score except for *Opportunity to choose shifts work*, *Work Schedule*, *Benefits Package*, and *Opportunities for career advancement*. This means that each individual area of job satisfaction has a significant effect on what aspect of their work environment that needs to be improved on for them to feel supported and integrated into the unit and vice-versa.

There is also a significant relationship between the nurses' choice on which aspect of their work environment that they are most satisfied about and 4 areas of their job satisfaction score: *Salary, Work Schedule, Benefits Package, and Weekends off per month*. This means that each mentioned area of job satisfaction has a significant on what aspect of their work environment that they are most satisfied about and vice-versa.

Lastly at 5% level of significance, there is sufficient evidence to conclude that the nurses' choice on which aspect of their work environment that they are most unsatisfied about, and all areas of job satisfaction have a significant relationship. This means that each individual area of job satisfaction has a significant effect on what aspect of their work environment that they are most unsatisfied about and vice-versa.

Overall, at 5% level of significance, the job satisfaction ratings of nurses and every facet of clinical readiness are significantly correlated. This indicates that the degree of clinical preparation exhibited by nurses is directly impacted by their job happiness, and vice versa. Staff involvement in their self-evaluation of competency performance may be considered. Whereas a performance review looks at how effectively a person does the work, a competency assessment determines if a person has the knowledge, training, experience, or skills necessary to execute it.

Table 10 shows the Spearman's rho coefficient with their corresponding p-value for each area of job satisfaction and overall comfort and confidence of nurses.

Table 10

Spearman's rho coefficient with their corresponding p-value for each area of job satisfaction and overall comfort and confidence of nurses

Areas of Job Satisfaction	Overall Comfort and Confidence	
	rho	p-value
Overall Job Satisfaction	.174	.034
Salary	.078	.344
Vacation	.201	.014
Workload	-.046	.578
Work Schedule	.127	.123
Benefits Package	.125	.129
Weekends off per month	.126	.126
Opportunity to choose shifts work	.080	.334

Amount of encourage and feedback	.230	.005
Opportunities for career advancement	.265	.001

There is enough data, at the 5% level of significance, to draw the conclusion that the nurses' overall work satisfaction and their overall comfort and confidence ratings are significantly correlated.

The Spearman's rho correlation ($\rho = .174$) shows a weak uphill (positive) linear relationship between the perceived level of overall job satisfaction and the overall comfort and confidence score of the nurses. Increases in overall job satisfaction are correlated with a higher degree of comfort and confidence in work of the nurses.

This may indicate that the nurses are more satisfied in their work as when they are more comfortable and confident in their work and environment. The Spearman's rho correlation for Vacation ($\rho = .201$), Amount of Encouragement and Feedback ($\rho = .230$), and Opportunities for career advancement ($\rho = .265$) show a weak uphill (positive) linear relationship which indicates that the increases in satisfaction in these areas is correlated an increase of the degree of comfort and confidence in work of the nurses.

This supports that the nurses are more satisfied in those areas when they are more comfortable and confident in their work and environment. The researcher being a nurse manager have been confronted of some staff with poor performance and frequent absences, thus immediately, the researchers' deal with it immediately and does not wait for the annual evaluation as this may lead to bad habits tolerance which may be the cause entrenchment and resentment which may hinder the growth of the team. Furthermore, in order to avoid obstructing or confusing the message while providing performance comments, be upfront and honest.

Chapter V

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In summary, this study described the factors associated with the level of clinical work preparedness and job satisfaction among critical care nurses in a tertiary hospital in Tabuk, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. In particular, this study aimed to ascertain: (1) the critical work readiness of critical care nurses; (2) the degree of job satisfaction regarding pay, vacation, benefits, monthly weekends off, degree of responsibility, prospects for career growth, degree of encouragement and feedback, and ability to select shift work; (3) the correlation between the critical care nurses' sociodemographic characteristics and their level of clinical work readiness; (4) the correlation between their job satisfaction and their sociodemographic characteristics; and (5) the correlation between their level of clinical work readiness and their job satisfaction.

There were 149 respondents in this study from ages below 30 years old and above. They were grouped as 30 years old and below, from age 31 to 40 years old and elderly from age 41 years old and above. More than half of the respondents are between the 31-40 years group (58.4%). The majority of the respondents were married at 59.7%. The length of hospital stay is at 5-10 years at 51.7%. There is a strong correlation between all facets of clinical readiness and the work satisfaction of nurses. The comfort and confidence of nurses are positively correlated with their total job satisfaction.

Conclusion

The study's findings indicate a strong correlation between the nurses' job happiness and every facet of clinical readiness. According to Romeo et al. (2013), professional growth and motivating factors are the paths to increased work satisfaction, with nurses reporting an overall moderate degree of job satisfaction.

This supported the theory that workers who have more "challenging, interesting, and enriching" work experience report greater levels of job satisfaction. Decision-making, compensation and benefits, work schedules, staffing, and workload were shown to have the lowest satisfaction levels in the same survey. Work experience, age, and nursing education are a few examples of factors that affect job satisfaction.

A study conducted by Yen-Ju Lin, Wan, Hsu, Hung, Juan, and Lin (2012) on employee satisfaction among physicians and nurses from 119 hospital-based CCUs in Taiwan compared the CCU culture as it relates to job satisfaction and intent to leave.

The study's conclusions were that while work satisfaction was positively correlated with adhocracy culture, job satisfaction among CCU nurses was not influenced by culture. A dynamic, imaginative, and creative work environment that emphasizes leaders as creative and visionary, as well as quick expansion and resource acquisition, are the hallmarks of an adhocracy. They discovered that the majority of CCUs had a strong market culture and hierarchy, which nurses link to low levels of work satisfaction. They urged CCU leadership to improve work happiness by introducing adhocracy into their organizational culture. Increased dedication to mentorship and orientation programs boosts work satisfaction and nurse retention, according to studies.

Recommendations

With the foreknown results and implications, the following were recommended:

To Human Resource Planners

Clinical work preparedness of nurses is an important indicator of quality of care provided by hospitals. The results of this study can be used by human resource planners to address areas requiring improvement. Human resource managers of Ministry of Health must look into the formulation to solve the problem regarding staffing shortage. In order to correctly employ the staffing formula and prevent both overstaffing and understaffing, they may adopt a standardized patient categorization method based on patient acuity. Enhancement of pay level according to annual performance evaluation and benefit package, salary differential for staff nurses working on weekends and night shift may also be taken of utmost consideration. The Human Resource Planner may include in their planning of staffing requirements with considerations to recruitment of proactive and multi-talented staff.

The Human Resource Planner of Ministry of Health may create programs for staff development and support nursing administration in the hospital for the development retention program of the highly skilled and competent nurses to be retained. The health care institution /nursing administration may follow through the identified performance deficiencies and promote a learning environment that support research development for future research. Continuing education and training on the skills and procedure performance, comfort and confidence and work environment for staff nurses to improve nursing care behaviors and raise awareness on the different factors that influence patient care. Critical care nurses' level of preparedness may be associated with job satisfaction. Improving nurse staffing and training, may improve the patient experience and the quality of care of nurses holds promise for enhancing job satisfaction. The administration may ensure that nurses have the strategies and the needed preparation to practice good patient communication and

teamwork. Hospitals may also ensure that there are enough nurses on staff to warrant nurses having the time to practice patient services at the critical care unit.

In addition, the Human Resource Planner may improve the benefit and vacation package for better job satisfaction and to decrease the employee turnover, as it is evidenced on this study in which vacation is the gratifying aspects of job satisfaction.

To Nursing Practice and Research

There may be a need for nurses to improve the level of work preparedness especially in the critical care unit. Nursing administration may consider the importance of orientation and may increase commitment for its improvement. Having a structured orientation is a good practice as they are trained to organizational policies and procedure. Different levels of orientation program may be considered such as for novice, those with experienced or competent in critical care unit and expert to cater to their particular learning needs. Unit nurse educator may conduct seminars, trainings, in-service lectures and workshop on skills and procedures needed in critical care unit, may enhance their clinical learning and job satisfaction as it creates meaningful patient care. Having a variety of instructional materials on hand, such as pamphlets or films, that nurses may share with patients is also beneficial. Staff nurses may utilize different strategies to practice good patient communication and teamwork leading to an improved interpersonal relationship with patients. Preceptorship may help newly qualified nurses develop the confidence to practice competency as a critical care nurse.

Further research should be undertaken to give clarity and elucidate factors that may influence work preparedness and job satisfaction as seen from the nurses assigned at the critical care unit of hospitals.

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Appendices

APPENDIX A

Letter Request to Conduct the Study

July 5, 2020

Name of the Hospital Administrator

Administrator

Name of the Hospital

Tabuk, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia

Dear (Name of the Hospital Administrator):

Greetings!

At present, I am planning to conduct a study entitled: ***Clinical Work Preparedness and Job Satisfaction of the Intensive Critical Care Nurses in a Tertiary Hospital in Saudi Arabia*** as an academic requirement to my course leading to the degree Master of Arts in Nursing in the UP Open University.

In view of this, I would like to request for your approval to conduct the study among the new and senior intensive critical care nurses in the hospital. Please be assured that the collected data will be confidential and will be solely used for the purpose of the study. I am intending to gather my data on August 2020. Also, may I request for your approval so I could obtain a complete list of names of the intensive critical care nurses in the hospital.

I am hoping for your favorable action regarding my requests. Thank you.

Sincerely yours,

(Sgd) MAY AILEEN DARROCA, R.N.

Resercher

Appendix B

Letter of Invitation to Respondents

July 10, 2020

Name of Nurse Nurse Staff Unit Assigned

Dear (Name of Respondent):

Greetings!

At present, I am planning to conduct a study entitled: ***Clinical Work Preparedness and Job Satisfaction of the Intensive Critical Care Nurses in a Tertiary Hospital in Saudi Arabia*** as an academic requirement to my course leading to the degree Master of Arts in Nursing in the UP Open University.

I am writing to invite you serve as one of the respondents of my study. The primary purpose of this inquiry is to determine the clinical learning environment and work motivation in relation to your socio-demographic characteristics like age, civil status, educational attainment, length of experience in the intensive critical care, length of hospital experience, and type of critical unit. I would like to assure you that the answers you are going to give in the research tool will be confidential, will not be used be used against you, and will be solely used for the purpose of the study.

I am hoping for your positive response and full cooperation to complete this study. Kindly let me know soonest of your response to this invitation, so we could meet for your signing of the Informed Consent form and for the copy of the questionnaire that you will answer.

Thank you.

Sincerely yours,

(Sgd.) MAY AILEEN DARROCA, R.N.

Researcher

Appendix C

Letter Requests to Utilize Casey-Fink Graduate Nurse Experience Survey Tool and Approval from Author

May 12, 2020

Name of the Author/s

Author of the Casey-Fink Graduate Nurse Experience Survey Tool Address

Dear (Name of the Author):

Greetings!

At present, I am planning to conduct a study entitled: ***Clinical Work Preparedness and Job Satisfaction of the Intensive Critical Care Nurses in a Tertiary Hospital in Saudi Arabia*** as an academic requirement to my course leading to the degree Master of Arts in Nursing in the UP Open University. The primary purpose of this inquiry is to determine the clinical work preparedness and job satisfaction in relation to your socio-demographic characteristics like age, civil status, educational attainment, length of experience in the intensive critical care, length of hospital experience, and type of critical unit.

In view of this, I would like to request for your approval if I could use the Casey-Fink Graduate Nurse Experience Survey tool you have developed. Please be assured that the mentioned tool will be solely used for the purpose of the study.

I am hoping for your favorable action regarding my request. Thank you.

Sincerely yours,

(Sgd) MAY AILEEN DARROCA, R.N.

Researcher

Fink, Regina <Regina.Fink@ucdenver.edu>

To: May Aileen Darroca

Cc: Queenie Roxas-Ridulme, Kathy Casey

Apr 30 at 2:35 PM

May Aileen- I am currently out of the country on vacation. You are welcome to use our survey but need to complete our survey.

Kathy- can you answer this email when you can and provide May with our website? Thanks.

Regina

Regina Fink

PhD APRN CHPN AOCN FAAN

Associate Professor

University of Colorado Anschutz Medical Campus, College of Nursing and School of Medicine

Aurora, Colorado 80045

303.724.9192 o

303.886.8655 c

Regina.fink@ucdenver.edu

Appendix D

Hospital Approval to Conduct Study

June 10, 2019

Mr. Saleh Al Balawi
Nursing Director
King Fahd Specialist Hospital
Tabuk, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia

Dear Mr. Saleh:

Greetings!

At present, I am planning to conduct a study entitled: *Clinical Work Preparedness and Job Satisfaction of the Critical Care Nurses in a Tertiary Hospital in Saudi Arabia* as an academic requirement to my course leading to the degree Master of Arts in Nursing in the University of the Philippines Open University.

In view of this, I would like to request for your approval to conduct the study among the new and senior critical care nurses in the hospital. Please be assured that the collected data will be confidential and will be solely used for the purpose of the study. I am intending to gather my data on July 2019. Also, may I request for your approval so I could obtain a complete list of names of the critical care nurses in the hospital.

I am hoping for your favorable action regarding my requests.

Thank you.

Sincerely yours,

(Sgd) MAY AILEEN DARROCA, R.N.
Researcher

10 7
1440
سالم البلوي
Saleh Al Balawi
مدير التمريض
مستشفى الملك فهد التخصصي
تبوك
رئيس التمريض
Hospital Director.

June 10, 2019

Dr. Tariq Al Balawi
Hospital Director
King Fahd Specialist Hospital
Tabuk, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia

Dear Dr. Tariq:

Greetings!

At present, I am planning to conduct a study entitled: *Clinical Work Preparedness and Job Satisfaction of the Critical Care Nurses in a Tertiary Hospital in Saudi Arabia* as an academic requirement to my course leading to the degree Master of Arts in Nursing in the University of the Philippines Open University.

In view of this, I would like to request for your approval to conduct the study among the new and senior critical care nurses in the hospital. Please be assured that the collected data will be confidential and will be solely used for the purpose of the study. I am intending to gather my data on July 2019. Also, may I request for your approval so I could obtain a complete list of names of the critical care nurses in the hospital.

I am hoping for your favorable action regarding my requests.

Thank you.

Sincerely yours,

(Sgd) **MAY AILEEN DARROCA, R.N.**
Researcher

training dept
تدريب

Appendix E

Informed Consent Form

Title of the : Clinical Work Preparedness and Job Satisfaction Among Critical Nurses in a Tertiary Hospital in Saudi Arabia

Researcher: **May Aileen Darroca**
Student, Master of Arts in Nursing
Faculty of Management and Development Studies Home
Address: Block 4 Lot 18 CDI, Calumpang, Molo, Iloilo City
5000 Philippines
Contact No: +63 9561528383
Email address: mayaileendarroca@yahoo.com

Purpose of the Study

This will be a study to determine the factors associated with level of clinical work preparedness and job satisfaction among critical care nurses in a tertiary hospital in Tabuk, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia.

Specifically, this study will seek answers to the following questions:

1. What is the level of clinical work preparedness of the critical care nurses in terms of -
 - 1.1 Skills and procedure performance;
 - 1.2 Comfort and confidence; and
 - 1.3 Work environment and difficulty of role transition?
2. What is the level of job satisfaction of the critical care nurses in terms of -
 - 2.1 Salary;
 - 2.2 Vacation;
 - 2.3 Work load;
 - 2.4 Work schedule;
 - 2.5 Benefits package;
 - 2.6 Weekends off per month;
 - 2.7 Opportunity to choose shifts work;
 - 2.8 Amount of encouragement and feedback; and
 - 2.9 Opportunities for career advancement?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the level of clinical work preparedness and the socio-demographic characteristics of the critical care nurses in terms of -
 - 3.1 Age;
 - 3.2 Civil Status;
 - 3.3 Educational attainment;

- 3.4 Length of experience in the intensive critical care;
- 3.5 Length of hospital experience; and
- 3.6 Type of intensive critical care unit?
- 4. Is there a relationship between the job satisfaction and the socio-demographic characteristics of the critical care nurses in terms of –
 - 4.1 Age;
 - 4.2 Civil Status;
 - 4.3 Educational attainment;
 - 4.4 Length of experience in the critical care;
 - 4.5 Length of hospital experience; and
 - 4.6 Type of critical care unit?
- 5. Is there a significant relationship between the level of clinical work preparedness and the job satisfaction of the critical care nurses?

Voluntary Participation

Your participation in this study is voluntary. You may withdraw from participation in this study anytime without any consequences or penalties. This study is also not related to your work contract.

Procedures

You will be asked to complete a questionnaire attached with this consent. The researcher will be available for any clarifications. Upon completion, the questionnaire will be submitted to the researcher.

Potential Risks and Procedures

There are anticipated risks in your participation. You will be protected against physical, psychological or emotional harm and your right to privacy and dignity will be preserved. When you feel discomfort upon responding to some questions, please feel free to approach the investigator.

Potential Benefits to Respondents

You will not directly benefit from your participation in this study. The objective of this study is to determine the factors associated with the level of work preparedness and job satisfaction of the critical care nurses.

Financial Compensation

You will not receive compensation or any amount in money for this study.

Confidentiality

Any information that is obtained in connection with this study will solely be used for the purpose of analyses and findings of this study. Your name and any pertinent information will not be revealed to anyone.

Contact Person

If you have any concern regarding the research and your rights as the respondent of this study, you may contact –

MAY AILEEN DARROCA

Contact No: +63 9561528383

Email address: mayailleendarroca@yahoo.com

Consent Form

By signing this document, I attest that I have read and understood the above information and have been given the opportunity to consider and ask questions. The researcher has answered all my questions and clarified all my concerns. I have also received a copy of this form and voluntarily agreed to participate in this study.

PRINTED NAME OVER SIGNATURE OF
RESPONDENT

DATE AND TIME

Name of Witness and Signature:

_____ Date : _____

Researcher's Signature

I, the researcher, certify that the respondent signing this consent form has read the above information fully, that it has been carefully explained to him/her, and that he/she fully understood the nature, risks, and benefits of his/her participation in this study.

PRINTED NAME OVER SIGNATURE OF
RESEARCHER

DATE AND TIME

Appendix F

Research Tool

FACTORS ASSOCIATED WITH LEVEL OF CLINICAL WORK PREPAREDNESS AND JOB SATISFACTION AMONG CRITICAL CARE NURSES IN A TERTIARY HOSPITAL IN SAUDI ARABIA

By

May Aileen Darroca

A QUESTIONNAIRE

Dear Respondents,

Kindly choose your answer and marked the space provided for your answers either with a check (/) or a circle. Please do not skip an item.

-
- I. Personal Characteristics
 1. Name: (Optional)

 2. Age (as of last birthday): _____
 3. Civil Status: ___Single ___Married ___Widow ___Common-in law
 4. Education Background : _____Diploma in Nursing ___Bachelor of Science in
Nursing
_____Master in Nursing ___Others, Specify:

 5. Length of Intensive Critical Care Experience:

 6. Length of hospital work experience ___less than 5 years ___5 to 10
years
_____ More than 10 years
 7. Type of Intensive Critical Care Unit:
_____medical, including coronary care
_____surgical, including trauma and cardiovascular
_____neonatal and pediatric
_____medical-surgical.
 8. Hospital ownership enrolled in: ___government owned ___privately owned

II. **Perception of the Clinical Work Preparedness** (Adopted from the Casey-Fink Graduate Nurse Experience Survey Tool)

A. Skills and Procedure Performance

List the top three skills/procedures you are *uncomfortable performing* independently at this time? (please select from the drop down list)

Skills/Procedures	Rank
1. Functions in accordance with legislation, on laws, organizational regulations and by-laws, which affect nursing practice.	
2. Provides care to meet individual patient on a 24-hour basis.	
3. Practices current critical care nursing tently.	
4. Delivers nursing care in a way that can be ethically justified.	
5. Demonstrates accountability for his/her sional judgment and actions.	
6. Creates and maintains an environment promotes safety and security of patients, s and staff.	
7. Masters the use of all essential equipment, available services and supplies for immediate f patients.	
8. Protects the patients from developing environmental induced infection.	
9. Utilizes the nursing process in an explicit natic manner to achieve the goals of care.	
10. Carries out health education for promotion and maintenance of health.	
11. Acts to enhance the professional pment of self and others.	
12. I am independent in all skills.	

B. Please answer each of the following questions by placing a mark in the appropriate column:

Statements	Strong agree 1	Disagr	Agr	Stron agree 4
1. I feel confident communicating with physicians.				
2. I am comfortable knowing what to do for a patient.				
3. I feel comfortable delegating tasks to the ng Assistant.				
4. I feel at ease asking for help from other RNs the unit.				
5. I am having difficulty prioritizing patient eeds.				
6. I feel my preceptor provides encouragement edback about my work.				

7. I feel staff is available to me during new ions and procedures.				
8. I feel overwhelmed by my patient care responsibilities and workload.				
9. I feel supported by the nurses on my unit.				
10. I have opportunities to practice skills and procedures more than once.				
11. I feel comfortable communicating with nts and their families.				
12. I am able to complete my patient care ment on time.				
13. I feel the expectations of me in this job are realistic.				
14. I feel prepared to complete my job nsibilities.				
15. I feel comfortable making suggestions for es to the nursing plan of care.				
16. I am having difficulty organizing patient needs.				
17. I feel I may harm a patient due to my lack of ledge and experience.				
18. There are positive role models for me to ve on my unit.				
19. My preceptor is helping me to develop confidence in my practice.				
20. I am supported by my family/friends.				
21. I am satisfied with my chosen nursing specialty.				
22. I feel my work is exciting and challenging.				
23. I feel my manager provides encouragement edback about my work.				
24. I am experiencing stress in my personal life.				

25. If you chose agree or strongly agree, to #24, please indicate what is causing your stress. (You may circle more than once choice.)

- a. Finances
- b. Child care
- c. Loans
- d. Living situation
- e. Personal relationships
- f. Job performance
- g. Others (please specify) _____

C. Transition and Work Environment (please circle any or all that apply)

1. What difficulties, if any, are you currently experiencing with the transition from the other hospital units to the intensive critical care unit?

- a. role expectations (e.g. autonomy, more responsibility, being a preceptor or in charge)
- b. lack of confidence (e.g. MD/PT communication skills, delegation, knowledge deficit, critical thinking)
- c. workload (e.g. organizing, prioritizing, feeling overwhelmed, ratios, patient acuity)

- d. fears (e.g. patient safety)
 - e. orientation issues (e.g. unit familiarization, learning technology, relationship with multiple preceptors, information overload)
 - f. Others (please specify)
-

2. What could be done to help you feel more supported or integrated into the unit?

- a. improved orientation (e.g. preceptor support and consistency, orientation extension, unit specific skills practice)
 - b. increased support (e.g. manager, RN, and educator feedback and support, mentorship)
 - c. unit socialization (e.g. being introduced to staff and MDs, opportunities for staff socialization)
 - d. improved work environment (e.g. gradual ratio changes, more assistance from unlicensed personnel, involvement in schedule and committee work)
 - e. Others (please specify)
-

3. What aspects of your work environment are most satisfying?

- a. peer support (e.g. belonging, team approach, helpful and friendly staff)
- b. patients and families (e.g. making a difference, positive feedback, patient satisfaction, patient interaction)

- c. ongoing learning (e.g. preceptors, unit role models, mentorship)
 - d. professional nursing role (e.g. challenge, benefits, fast pace, critical thinking, empowerment)
 - e. positive work environment (e.g. good ratios, available resources, great facility, up-to-date technology)
 - f. Others (please specify)
-

4. What aspects of your work environment are least satisfying?

- a. nursing work environment (e.g. unrealistic ratios, tough schedule, futility of care)
 - b. system (e.g. outdated facilities and equipment, small workspace, charting, paperwork)
 - c. interpersonal relationships (e.g. gossip, lack of recognition, lack of teamwork, politics)
 - d. orientation (inconsistent preceptors, lack of feedback)
 - e. Others (please specify)
-

III. Perceived Job Satisfaction

How *satisfied* are you with the following aspects of your job:

Aspects	Very satisfied 1	Moderately satisfied 2	Neither satisfied or Dissatisfied 3	Moderately satisfied 4	Very satisfied 5
1. Salary					
2. Vacation					
3. Benefits package					
4. Hours that you work					
5. Weekends off per month					
6. Your amount of responsibility					
7. Opportunities for career cement					
8. Amount of encouragement and back					
9. Opportunity to choose worked					

Appendix G

Research Timeline

This research work will be accomplished in 12 weeks. Details of the activities are enumerated below.

Activity	Schedule
Presentation and Defense of the Research Proposal	Week 1
Submission of Letter of Request to the Hospital Administrator	Week 2
Submission of the Application to the Ethics Board	Week 3 to Week 4
Sending of Letter of Invitation to the ICU nurses	Week 5
Finalization of the List of Study Participants	Week 6
Sending of Letter Request to Authors of the Tools Regarding Adoption in the Present Study	Week 6 to 7
Signing of Consent Forms	Week 7
Finalization of the Research Tool	Week 8
Data Collection	Week 8
Data encoding and processing	Week 9
Research Report Writing	Week 10
Submission of Research Report	Week 11
Presentation of the Research Report	Week 11
Finalization of the Research Report	Week 12

Appendix H

Budgetary Requirement

Office Supplies	Php3,358.
00	
Computer Ink (4 cartridges @ Php400.00) Bond Paper (5 reams @ Php250.00) Folders (10 pcs. @ Php10.00)	
Pencil (3 pcs @ Php6.00) Ballpens (5 pcs @ Php20.00)	
Letter Envelopes (160 pcs. @ Php1.50) Brown Envelopes (10 pcs @ Php5.00)	
Printing/Xerox	Php2,550.
00	
Research Instrument (6 pages x 300 copies @ Php 0.75) Informed Consent Forms (2 pages x 300 copies @ Php 0.75) Drafts and Other Documents (200 pages x 5 copies @ Php 0.75)	
Transportation Expenses	Php10,000.00
Food and Tokens	Php5,000.00
Book Binding (5 copies @ Php400.00)	
	Php2,000.
00 Ring Binding (5 copies @ Php100.00)	
Php500.00	
Professional Fees	Php22,000.00
Editor (@ Php 5,000.00) Encoder (@ Php8,000.00) Statistician (@ Php5,000.00)	
Computer analyst (@ Php4,000.00)	
TOTAL	<u>Php45,408.00</u>

Appendix I

CLINICAL WORK PREPAREDNESS AND JOB SATISFACTION AMONG CRITICAL CARE NURSES IN A TERTIARY HOSPITAL IN SAUDI ARABIA

By

May Aileen Darroca

Pre-testing was done to assess whether the survey questionnaire has captured the responses that was expected to be collected. Pre-testing was needed to clarify whether the questionnaire was easy to understand and if further changes in the questionnaire were necessary. Reliability Analysis was then conducted to determine whether the scales or test items used in the questionnaire consistently reflects the construct it is measuring. The computed Cronbach's alpha indicates the internal consistency of a set of scales or test items.

- Level of Comfort and Confidence (Part IIB)

Twenty-four (24) scale items from the questionnaire that aims to evaluate the perceived level of comfort and confidence in clinical work, all of which were measured using a four-point scale ranging from 1=Strongly Disagree to 4=Strongly Agree were tested.

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.875	24

Cronbach's alpha is **0.875**, which indicates a high level of internal consistency for the scale. That is, these 24 items reliably measure the same latent variable, which is the perceived level of comfort and confidence in clinical work.

CURRICULUM VITAE

MAY AILEEN BACTING DARROCA, BSN-RN

Block 4 Lot 18 CDI, Calumpang, Iloilo City 5000 Philippines

Mobile# +63 9561528383

mayaileendarroca@yahoo.com Professional License No. 0265396

Reg. No. 09-J-N-0265608

Education:

- Bachelor of Science in Nursing, University of Iloilo, March 1994
- Master of Arts in Nursing (candidate), University of the Philippines Open University

Examination Hurdled:

- Board Passer for Professional Licensure Examination- Registered Nurse No. 0265396
- Saudi Commission for Health Specialist Examination- Nurse Specialist License No. 09-J-N-0265608

Machines Handled:

- Incubators: Omnibed Giraffe Incubator, Drager Caleo Incubator
- Ventilators: Hamilton, Servo-I, E-360, Bear Cub,
- Hypothermic Machine: Tecotherm Neo
- IVAC machine & Syringe Pump
- HFO ventilator:
- Radiant warmer: Panda,
- Intensive phototherapy/ Bilirubin lights
- Breast milk pump
- Trans illuminator
- Bubble CPAP: Drager
- Cardiopulmonary monitor: Philips, Drager

WORKING EXPERIENCE WITH JOB DESCRIPTION:

DEC. 29, 2012 – NOV. 29, 2016 **NICU- Head Nurse**
PICU-Acting Head Nurse King Khalid Civilian Hospital
Ministry Of Health Tabuk, K.S.A.

SEPT. 9, 2008 – AUGUST 13, 2012: **Charge Nurse**

Neonatal Intensive Care Unit

Ministry of Defense & Aviation

King Fahd Armed Forces Hospital Jeddah, KSA

JUNE 11, 2002 – APRIL 6, 2008 **Staff/ Charge Nurse**

Pediatric & Neo-natal Intensive Care Unit Ministry of Health, Children's Hospital Taif City,
Kingdom of Saudi Arabia

APRIL 3, 2001- MARCH 22, 2002

Staff Nurse in Male Medical Ward

Ministry of Health

King Fahd Specialist Hospita

Al-Qassim, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia

SEPTEMBER 1998-JANUARY 29, 2000: **PRIVATE DUTY NURSE**

Mrs. Rudelyn Wolters Ledesco Village, Blk.1 Lot 2

La Paz, Iloilo, Philippines

JANUARY 1996-JULY 1998:

DISTRICT SALES MANAGER

Gerden Commercial and Company Incorporation

Tabuc Suba, Jaro, Iloilo City, Philippines

TRAININGS and SEMINARS ATTENDED

- The International Quality and Patient Safety Conference
Park Hyatt Hotel Jeddah November 3-5, 2015
- Neonatal-Perinatal Update 2015
King Faisal Specialist Hospital & Research Centre October 7, 2015
- Basic Cardiac Life Support (Provider Course) Saudi Heart Association, Tabuk, KSA
April 8, 2015
- 4th, 5th, 6th, 7th International Neonatal Conference - 2010 Hotel Intercontinental, Jeddah, KSA
February 2009, 2011, 2012
- Neonatal Resuscitation Program (NRP) Provider Course King Fahd Armed Forces Hospital,
Jeddah, KSA February 28, 2009 and February 27, 2011
- Leadership and Management Preceptor Course
King Fahd Armed Forces Hospital, Jeddah June 20, 2011
- Charge Nurse Course
King Fahd Armed Forces Hospital, Jeddah September 20, 2010

- 21st Century NICU CARE January 23, 2012
- S.T.A.B.L.E.
Advance Course for Neonatal Nursing Feb. 14 – 15, 21, 2009
Education and Training Center Auditorium
King Fahd Armed Forces Hospital, Jeddah, KSA

Kingdom of Saudi Arabia Ministry of Health
General Directorate of Health Affairs in Tabuk Region King Fahad Specialist Hospital
NURSING OFFICE SERVICES

INDEX COMPTETENCY CHECKLIST

II. Probationary Competency

1. Monitoring patient's vital signs and knowledge of acceptable deviation from the norm.
2. Medications administration
3. Intravenous therapy (insertion, maintenance, discontinuing
4. Operation of blood sugar testing equipment
5. Use of pulse oximetry

III. General Competency

1. Patient falls (assessment of risk and methods to prevent falls).
2. Nursing role in cardiac/respiratory arrest.
3. Use of blood, blood products, and blood-related procedures (e.g., phlebotomy and blood administration.)
4. Assessment/reassessment of patients according to the scope of services (e.g. critical care, labor and delivery, and surgical units).
5. Skin care and prevention and care of pressure ulcers.

IV. Specific/Departmental Competency ICU, CCU, NICU CARDIAC WARD

1. Assisting physician in placing central lines or arterial lines
2. Obtaining arterial blood gas samples
3. Care of patients with tracheostomies
4. Recognizing critical ECG changes including arrhythmia.